

THE RELATIONSHIP OF LANGUAGE EXPOSURE AND LANGUAGE COMPETENCE AMONG ENGLISH MAJOR STUDENTS: A CONVERGENT PARALLEL APPROACH

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The Relationship of Language Exposure and Language Competence among English Major Students: A Convergent Parallel Approach

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Abstract

The purpose of this study was to identify the significant relationships between language exposure and language competence among English major students in a local college. Also, this aimed to explore the lived experiences, coping mechanism, and insight of the students related to their language exposure and language competence. This study used mixed method design, utilizing parallel convergent approach. The participants of the study were the mathematics education students from all year levels. For the quantitative part, it involved 214 students from all year levels and for the qualitative part, it involved 10 participants. Result revealed that the level of language exposure and language competence is high which means it is oftentimes manifested by the English major students. Meanwhile, for the qualitative results it revealed different experiences, coping mechanisms, and insight of the students relative to their exposure with the language and language competence. Similarly, mixed method analysis and data corroboration found that both quantitative and qualitative data are merging. The results showed that being exposed to the language greatly improves English major students' language skills, helping them use the language effectively and efficiently in real-life situations.

Keywords: *language exposure, language competence, mixed methods*

Introduction

In general, language competence displays the level of student's ability to speak, write, read, listen and comprehend regardless of how the specific target language will be used in various contexts. It is essential for students as it deals many opportunities such in effective communication, build connection among other cultures and especially, it secures growth and development for academic attainment on student's performance. However, EFL students find this a difficulty when conveying a particular viewpoint in some point of contexts, they are hindered to choose and feel a lack of adequate terminology to build their idea. Most of EFL students think first about their native language before translating it to English. In these circumstances, students who believed to have lower levels of language competence, more behavioral issues, and less academic achievement face these hurdles. Hence, there is a result of mismatch between developmental capability and academic expectation (Armea, 2022; Ghambir, 2020).

In global setting especially in Nepal, English language is taught as a foreign language from the elementary through the university level students. However, Nepalese students have a difficult time when speaking, reading and comprehending English even after earning their degrees. Along with the position of English in Nepal, there are so many problems in the context of English language teaching problems, but there are least of studies have been carried out to recommend solutions of these problems. In Thailand, students also faced difficulties in terms of language competence specifically in English language. Most of the students have lack of language skills as well knowledge and ability to use English in various social and academic contexts. Therefore, students may find it difficult to use the language in socializing and several factors that affects the student's potential when using the language. Hence, students have lack of language experience, such as grammatical capabilities, lack of vocabulary, knowledge and motivation to learn the language (Ghambir, 2020; Sasum & Weeks, 2019).

In the Philippine context, the country is recognized as one of the leading English-speaking nations among non-native speakers due to the emphasis on English education in schools and universities from kindergarten through college. English serves as the country's primary international language of communication, and a significant portion of the population demonstrates a certain level of proficiency. However, it is not widely known that Filipino students also encounter challenges in learning English, particularly in speaking. Some Filipinos struggle with English fluency or writing skills. Freshman English majors at the College of Teacher Education at Bestlink College, for instance, have experienced difficulties during their initial stages of tertiary education, specifically in areas such as grammar, vocabulary, and macro- skills, while facing fewer challenges in linguistics. Additionally, students are often hindered by the frequent use of their mother tongue, which remains prevalent in daily communication, limiting their English language exposure (Pachino, 2020; Evangelista et al., 2019).

Based from the previous citations presented above, it is highly observed that the language competence especially in English language throughout the world that there are difficulties within the students in each specific context. This phenomenon is evident both globally and nationally. In response, the researcher conducted this study to examine the underlying issues and challenges. The findings of this research aim to raise awareness among relevant authorities, such as the Commission on Higher Education (CHED) and the Department of Education (DepEd), highlighting the need to review and enhance their curricula and instructional practices to promote students' language competence in English. Additionally, teachers may utilize the study's findings to develop innovative techniques and strategies that can accelerate and enhance students' proficiency in speaking, listening, writing, reading, and comprehension skills. With this,

findings of the study are great help to the large mass or body in the society. Lastly, the researcher has observed that there are lot of studies have been conducted that is focusing on language competence of students regarded in English language. However, most of these studies have been conducted in global and national setting and only few studies have been conducted in the local setting. To cite some, the study of Lozano et al. (2020) which focuses on language competence and academic performance of the students by which, it is descriptive by its nature. Also, the study of (Aguelo, 2017) which focuses on enhancing the student's language competence through collaborative learning. Moreover, these studies are different from the present study as the study focuses on language exposure of the English major students in accordance to their language competence by a convergent parallel study highlighting on its effect in their competence through speaking, listening, writing, reading and comprehension of the English language. Hence, the present study fill the gap that previous studies failed to examine and explore making new results and findings essential and significant in the field of teaching.

This served as the basis for the institution for adhering developments needed for the program, concerning the needs of English major students solely to the purpose of enhancing their language competence. Also, this could be an advantage for the English major students as they could get insights that are related to the strategies effective to enhance and develop their current language competence to their full potential. Further, study serves as an embodiment of knowledge which includes presentations and publication in scientific forums or journals to share the study's findings contributed to the broader body of knowledge within their field of study.

Research Questions

Specifically, this study sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the level of language exposure and language competence among English major students?
2. Is there a significant relationship between language exposure and language exposure among English major students?
3. What are the lived experiences and coping mechanism of English major students with regards to their language exposure in their language competence?
4. What are the insights of English major students with regards to the effectiveness of language exposure in developing language competence?
5. How do qualitative results explain the quantitative results of the study?

Methodology

Research Design

This study used a mixed methods research design in a convergent parallel approach, which combines both quantitative and qualitative methods concurrently. As defined by Johnson et al. (2017), mixed methods used quantitative and qualitative methods in a single or multiphase study. Also, it is an inquiry or an approach which investigate the social world that ideally involves more than one methodological tradition and thus more than one way of knowing, along with more than one kind of technique for gathering, analyzing, and representing human phenomena, all for the purpose of better understanding.

In this mixed-method study, a convergent parallel design was utilized to explore both quantitative and qualitative aspects of language education. The study collected survey data and conducted focus group discussions or one-on-one interviews simultaneously, giving equal weight to both types of data. The quantitative data from surveys provided statistical insights, while the qualitative data from interviews offered in-depth perspectives. These data sets were analyzed separately and then combined to identify connections, differences, and contradictions. This approach allowed for a comprehensive understanding of the relationships between the different data sources and enriched the interpretation of the findings (Hanson et al., 2005).

To gain a comprehensive understanding of the topic, this study employed the convergent parallel design, a mixed-method approach. In this approach, both qualitative and quantitative data were collected simultaneously during the same research phase, with each method given equal importance. The qualitative component involved in-depth interviews or focus groups, while the quantitative component involved surveys or statistical measures. Both datasets were analyzed separately to identify individual insights and then combined to compare and validate results. The goal was to triangulate the methods, using the strengths of both approaches to corroborate findings and enhance the overall understanding of the research topic (Demir & Pismek, 2018).

In a convergent parallel design, both qualitative and quantitative data are collected and analyzed concurrently to provide a comprehensive understanding of the research topic. For this study, data from qualitative sources such as in-depth interviews, focus group discussions, audio recordings, and transcriptions were gathered alongside quantitative data from survey questionnaires. The qualitative data were analyzed using discourse and thematic analysis to explore relationships and patterns related to language exposure and competence among students. Concurrently, statistical analysis was applied to the quantitative data to profile language exposure, assess competence, and identify significant differences and correlations. By comparing and integrating the results from both data types, this approach aimed to enrich the overall understanding of the research question.

Participants

In this section, the distribution and profile in gathering quantitative and qualitative data from the participants and informants as well as respondents of this study are discussed. Additionally, the exclusion criterion is based upon the statuses of English major students and

they must not be an irregular student of the said program on the first semester of the academic year 2023–2024.

Quantitative Phase

The respondents of this study were English major student from all year levels in Kapalong College Agriculture, Sciences and Technology during the second semester of S.Y. 2023-2024. They were chosen as the respondents because the study is about language exposure and language competence among English major students in a local college. The inclusion criteria guaranteed representation from enrolled students in Bachelor of Secondary Education major in English Program who maintained regular student status, were enrolled in the first semester of the academic year 2023–2024, and were enrolled in their respective courses, which was open to participants of any gender who demonstrated a willingness to participate. Conversely, the irregular students of the said program on the first semester of the academic year 2023–2024 was the exclusion criterion due from their hectic schedule inside the campus. Specifically, one-hundred four (104) first-year students, sixty-four (64) second-year students, thirty-two (32) third-year students and fourteen (14) fourth-year students were selected across all year levels of English major students, totaling two-hundred fourteen (214) participants for the first semester of the academic year 2023- 2024. Since, the study purports to involves students who are in the English major program in a local college, it would be fitting and valid to include English major students in Kapalong College of Agriculture Sciences and Technology. Further, the respondents were determined through sampling, specifically, stratified random sampling to establish randomness and maintain scientific rigor in the study. This method involves dividing population into smaller groups, or “strata”, and randomly selecting a sample from each stratum. The per-stratum samples were combined to create an overall stratified random sample. An alternative to simple random sampling, stratified random sampling ensures that each stratum is represented in the sample and can provide more accurate results when analyzing subgroups within the population (Nguyen et al., 2020)

Further, the researcher wrote a formal request letter to the college registrar to obtain access to the total population of English major education students from all year levels. The researcher gathered the data from the population of English major education students to compute the sample. After obtaining the data, the researcher sent the information to his statistician for computation of the study sample.

Qualitative Phase

In contrast, in the selection of the research participants, purposive sampling was used. Participants were selected who could best inform the research questions and enhance understanding of the phenomenon under study (Kuper et al., 2008). In the study, there were five (5) participants for the In-Depth Interview and another five (5) for the Focus Group Discussion. In addition, in selecting the qualified participants of the study, the following inclusion criteria were followed: (1) must be an enrolled Secondary Education major in English student; (2) could be chosen from any year level freshmen, sophomore, junior, or senior; (3) must be a regular student and not probationary nor irregular; (4) could be male or female; (5) must have the willingness to join and participate in the study.

Table 1.1. *Distribution of Respondents*

<i>Year Level</i>	<i>Population</i>	<i>Sample</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
First Year	223	104	22.85%
Second Year	136	64	13.94%
Third Year	69	32	7.07%
Fourth Year	29	14	2.97%
Total	457	214	46.83%

Table 1.2. *Profiles of the Participants*

<i>Assigned Code</i>	<i>Sex</i>	<i>Year-Level</i>
IDI-01	Female	First Year
IDI-02	Female	First Year
IDI-03	Female	Second Year
IDI-04	Male	Third Year
IDI-05	Female	Fourth Year
FGD-01	Female	First Year
FGD-02	Female	Second Year
FGD-03	Male	Third Year
FGD-04	Male	Third Year
FGD-05	Male	Fourth Year

Instrument

In this section, the research tools in gathering quantitative and qualitative data from the participants and informants as well as respondents of this study are discussed.

Quantitative Strand

In identifying the level and status of language exposure (LE) and language competence (LC), an adopted questionnaire from a published

and conducted study was used. Then, these questionnaires were contextualized in the current study according to its focus and context. After the researcher contextualized the research questionnaire, especially in the construct of each item under each variable, this was further validated and evaluated by external validators who were all experts in the field of research. Later on, the suggestions and recommendations of the evaluators were followed thoroughly to make the research tool more reliable. Also, the researcher ensured that the questions stipulated in the questionnaire used basic English in order for the respondents to answer each question and comprehend the purpose of the research.

Language Exposure. The questionnaire for this variable is adapted from the work of Magno, et al. (2009) which has four (4) indicators, namely: home, school, friends and media. The questionnaire adopted is composed of 23 items. The wording was adapted and simplified to make it more accessible for school students. The responses of the participants will be rated from never (1) as the lowest and always (5) as the highest.

Language Competence. The questionnaire for this variable were adopted from Eslit (2023) which has five indicators, namely: reading, writing, speaking, listening and comprehension. The reliability test conducted using Cronbach's alpha coefficient. The reliability gained on the test reaching .92 which makes the questionnaire reliable. The tool is a 50-item construct divided unevenly among the five stated indicators.

Qualitative Strand

In the qualitative phase, an interview guide was used, containing grand core questions and probing and supporting questions, which were used both in the in-depth interviews and focus group discussions. It was validated by external validators to check the construct of the questions, ensuring they measured what they intended to measure and would gather the necessary data for the study. Additionally, in this strand, the researcher used this validated interview guide to validate the results found in the quantitative phase of the study. The interview guide consisted of two parts: one for the letter of permission for the participants and the second for the interview proper.

Validity of the Instruments

The instruments used in the study underwent a validation process before being administered and distributed to the respondents. In the study, the survey questionnaires were adopted from published research that dealt with language exposure (LE) and language competence (LC). These studies underwent validation processes, and the Cronbach's alpha of the pilot testing was calculated. Additionally, the adopted questionnaires underwent pilot testing to check their reliability. Prior to the pilot testing, the questionnaires were validated by panelists to check their content and assess whether the tool measured what it was supposed to measure. These validators were all doctorate degree holders and experts in the field of research. The researcher considered this to ensure that the validators were credible and knowledgeable enough to validate the tool used in the study.

Additionally, the study used an interview guide to determine if the qualitative data corroborated with the quantitative results. Likewise, an informed consent form was used, which explained the purpose of the study. Participants were able to read the consent form to be aware and knowledgeable regarding their participation in the study. Similarly, participants were fully educated that their involvement was intentional and personal, and their identification and personal information would be kept with the highest confidentiality. Lastly, the whole interview process was held in distraction-free spaces and places that were most convenient for the participants.

Procedure

From the time when the researcher was done with the routing of the manuscript to its panelists, the research manuscript was submitted to the Research Ethics Committee of the KCAST to check whether the study followed the mandated protocol needed for ethical consideration and trustworthiness. The researcher also requested Ethics Clearance to conduct the study. After conforming to the recommendations as per protocol evaluation given by the Research Ethics Committee (REC) of the institution, the following stages were undertaken by the researcher in gathering the data needed for the study.

First, the researcher wrote a letter asking permission to conduct the study. A request letter was signed by the adviser and attached with an endorsement letter signed by the college president of Kapalong College of Agriculture, Sciences and Technology.

Meanwhile, before collecting data, the researcher conducted orientations with relevant personnel. These orientations aimed to familiarize the personnel with the study's nature and purpose. The researcher provided informed consent forms to these individuals, who then distributed them to the respondents along with the researcher. Following this, the researcher explained the study's goals and respondents' roles as outlined in the informed consent forms. After the orientation, respondents signed the forms, indicating their understanding of the study's purpose and their voluntary participation. After these essential and necessary preliminaries in conducting the study, discussed below are the different essential and significant measures in gathering the data both in the qualitative and quantitative phase of the study. By which, in the data gathering process, optimum confidentiality of data is assured.

Quantitative Strand

In the quantitative phase, the researcher conducted the study on a face-to-face basis, personally distributing the survey questionnaire to the participants. To be specific with data gathering processes, below are the different steps to be taken by the researcher:

First, after the respondents signed the informed consent form, they were given the survey questionnaire, which contained different questions for the two variables, language exposure (LE) and language competence (LC). In the questionnaire, the respondents did not need to include their name as it was optional. They were also given ample time to complete answering the questions to ensure valid and reliable answers were obtained;

Second, after the respondents completely answered all the stipulated questions in the survey questionnaire, the researcher completely retrieved the questionnaires in preparation for the tallying process. Consequently, the respondents were given a token of appreciation as a form of gratitude for their voluntary participation in the study. Additionally, in the tallying of the responses, a format of tallying the data was provided by the researcher to his statistician for easy treatment of the data afterwards;

Third, after tallying the research data, the analysis and treatment of the data followed. The tallied data was given to the research statistician who was capable and knowledgeable in data analysis and data treatment;

Fourth, when the statistician returned the result of the data analysis and treatment, the researcher analyzed and interpreted the results. Of course, this was done with the help and guidance of the research adviser to ensure that the analysis done was truthful and correct.

Lastly, in the whole process of the data gathering, data treatment, and data analysis and interpretation, it was guaranteed that the data taken from the research respondents would be kept confidential. All of the answered survey questionnaires were put in one box with a lock and a unique and strong pin code so that only the researcher could gain access to it. With these measures, it was guaranteed that no other person could access the gathered data.

Qualitative Strand

When the results and findings of the quantitative phase were already available, the data gathering under the qualitative phase began. The main purpose of the data gathering was to confirm and affirm results in the first phase through in-depth interviews and focus group discussions. In this phase, the researcher followed the following procedures:

First, since the respondents already signed the informed consent before the conduct of the quantitative phase, the researcher chose 10 participants from the same sample to be part of the in-depth interview and focus group discussion.

Second, when the 10 participants were already chosen and selected, another orientation was conducted. This orientation informed and educated these participants about the next stage of the research, fully informing them about their role in this stage of the research. In addition, in case any of the identified participants withdrew their participation during the orientation, the researcher respected and researcher looked for new participants and volunteers.

Third, after the orientation, a separate one-on-one interview with the first 5 informants started. This was conducted via Google Meet, over the phone, messenger, or any platforms that the informants wished to use. After the in-depth interview with the 5 informants, the focus group discussion with the remaining 5 participants started. This was conducted face-to-face agreed upon and convenient for the participants was utilized in the whole discussion.

Fourth, after the interview process, the researcher transcribed all of the individual responses of the 5 informants in verbatim form. Also, a separate transcript was prepared for the 5 participants in the focus group discussion.

Fifth, when the individual transcript of all the 10 informants was available as well as the transcript for the focus group discussion, the researcher gave each informant and participant a copy of this. This was for them to check and verify whether the transcript was correct or incorrect. In addition, if any of the participants wished to delete part of the transcript or add more responses, the researcher conformed and followed this.

Lastly, when the verified copy of the individual transcript from the 10 informants and the one from the focus group discussion was ready, the analysis of data, which is the thematic analysis, followed.

Data Analysis

In this section, the data analysis, sequence, emphasis, and mixing procedures as well as figure of procedures, anticipated methodological issues, trustworthiness of the study, validity of instruments and ethical considerations in gathering quantitative and qualitative data from the participants and informants as well as respondents of this study are discussed.

Quantitative Phase

The quantitative data was analyzed using descriptive statistics and Pearson-r. Here are the discussions to each of the statistical tool: (1) Mean was used to determine the level language exposure and language competence of English major students, to answer research questions or problem number 2; (2) Pearson-r was used to determine the significant relationship between language exposure and language competence of English major students; (3) Standard Deviation was used to measure how spread out the responses of the respondents are; (4) The survey data, which were collected, serving as the basis for in-depth analysis. Upon retrieval of the questionnaires, the data were tallied and treated accordingly. The survey data were further analyzed using Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) for both descriptive and inferential statistics. These statistical treatments were applied to ascertain the status of

English major students.

Qualitative Phase

In the qualitative phase, the data collected during the conduct of the interview was analyzed that came up with conclusions that affirmed and supported the findings in the quantitative phase. As explained, analysis of data in research involved summarizing the mass of data collected and presenting the results in a way that communicates the most important features of the study (Harding, 2013).

In the study, data analysis was done after the process of transcribing the results of the in-depth interview and focus group discussion among the participants. The researcher used coding and thematic analysis in analyzing the collected and gathered data. Further, in displaying and presenting the data, it was organized into different categories that have similar responses from the different participants. The process was called thematic analysis.

Regarding the qualitative data analysis, the researcher employed coding and thematic analysis. According to Braun & Clarke (2013) stated that thematic analysis is a flexible data analysis plan that qualitative researcher' used to generated themes from interview data. This involved examining the patterns and themes that emerged from the utterances or statements of the participants/informants during the one-on one and focus group interviews. The themes were formulated with the purpose of analyzing the lived experiences of English major student's language exposure and language competence. The data were carefully analyzed to identify and extract relevant themes that shed light on the research objectives and provide insights into the participant's experiences in this context.

To familiarize the data, the researcher listened and transcribed the recorded interview of the participants and keep on reading it to identify similar answers given by the participants. After familiarizing the data, coding of the data begun of which the researcher used coding of the data that arrived and generated themes, ideas and categories. Then similar passages of text were marked with a code label so that they can easily be retrieved at a later stage for further comparison and analysis.

After the codes was clustered together, the researcher labeled the clusters based on the meaning or relationships shared among the codes. Naming the codes was the next process involving the utilization of the labels created for the theme and providing a comprehensive name that describes the relationship or meaning conveyed in that specific theme.

Lastly, to enhance the reliability of the data, the researcher consulted a data analyst with expertise in the field and their research adviser for additional verification. The findings and interpretations were subsequently presented in tabular form to facilitate clearer understanding and detailed elaboration.

Ethical Considerations

To maintain the trust of the English teacher education students at KCAST, this study placed paramount importance on their safety, anonymity, full protection, and confidentiality. Steps were meticulously taken to address these ethical considerations with the aim of upholding the participants' trust throughout the duration of the research. The researcher scrupulously adhered to ethical principles, encompassing respect for individuals, beneficence, justice, securing informed consent, and preserving confidentiality, to guarantee the observance of ethical standards. These principles steered the execution of the study in a conscientious and considerate manner, with a focus on safeguarding the rights and welfare of the participants (Mack et al., 2005).

Respect for persons is a fundamental ethical principle that underscores the significance of treating research participants with politeness and consideration, while recognizing their independence in deciding their involvement in a study (Munhall, 2012 & Scott, 2013). This principle requires furnishing participants with comprehensive information about the study, ensuring their clear comprehension of the research, as well as any potential risks or benefits involved. Obtaining informed consent constitutes a pivotal component of abiding by this principle, signifying a voluntary agreement grounded in an informed comprehension. By upholding the principle of respect for persons, the researcher can guarantee that the study is conducted ethically and in a manner that respects the rights and autonomy of the participants.

Prior to conducting the interviews, the researcher secured the participants' consent and prearranged the interview schedule to prevent any conflicts with their academic commitments or other responsibilities. This proactive approach aimed to minimize any disruptions to the participants' schedules caused by the researcher's presence and to mitigate the necessity of rescheduling or canceling the interviews.

Throughout the course of the study, the researcher fostered a considerate and polite rapport with the participants, seeking their consent before recording conversations. If they did not allow recording, the researcher truthfully respected their decision. Likewise, the researcher encouraged participants to pose questions whenever they wished and upheld the confidentiality of both the in-depth interviews and the focus group discussions. Moreover, participants retained the prerogative and the free will to decline responding to sensitive inquiries about the study. If they wished to withdraw and terminate participation in the study, they had all the freedom to do so without any other explanation or risks imposed or involved. By cultivating a positive relationship and adhering to courteous conduct, the study was conducted in an ethical and respectful manner.

Consent constitutes a pivotal element of research ethics, serving to demonstrate respect for research participants. Through the learning of informed consent, participants are comprehensively apprised of the aims and rationale of the research in which they are invited to

engage. Written consent will be diligently procured from each participant, affirming their willingness to partake in the in-depth interviews and focus group discussions. Additionally, participants received detailed information about the study's outcomes and discoveries, thereby upholding transparency and ensuring that they remained well-informed throughout the research process (Creswell, 2012).

To uphold the ethical standards of the study, participants were furnished with permission and consent letters that comprehensively delineated the study's particulars, including its methods, design, procedures, benefits, and risks. These letters were designed to facilitate participants' comprehension of the study's nature and empower them to make informed decisions regarding their participation. Those who chose not to participate were free to do so without any obligation to provide explanations, and they received assurances that their data would be held in strict confidence. Furthermore, participants were informed of their right to receive the study's results. By adhering to these ethical guidelines, the study was conducted responsibly and respectfully.

Beneficence, as an ethical principle, underscores the dedication to mitigating risks and optimizing the welfare of research participants. In this study, measures were taken to safeguard and shield the well-being of the participants. The confidentiality of the interviewees was meticulously preserved to avert any potential threats to their privacy. Additionally, all data files were securely stored and never left unattended or inadequately protected (Bricki & Green, 2007).

To align with the principle of beneficence, measures were implemented to preserve the anonymity and confidentiality of participants' responses and personal information. Participants and respondents involved were informed of the findings to help them improve and enhance their language exposure and language competence as one of the benefits of the study. They were also given tokens of appreciation to show respect and generosity for their time given in the study. To mitigate and avoid potential risks, remote communication through a social media platform was opted for, avoiding face-to-face interactions with the participants. These precautions were undertaken to safeguard the participants' well-being and interests, underscoring the dedication to ethical research standards.

Additionally, the data gathered during this research study was exclusively utilized for the specified research objectives. However, the study's outcomes may also have been disseminated through various means, including presentations within the institution, publication in scientific forums or journals, and presentations at conferences, whether on a local, national, or international scale. The researcher's intent in sharing the study's findings was to contribute to the broader body of knowledge within their field of study.

Confidentiality was upheld through various techniques to protect the data, results, and findings, as well as to ensure the safety of participants. This encompassed concealing all personal identities of the participants and refraining from disclosing them. Furthermore, all materials, including audio records, encoded transcripts, notes, soft and hard copies of data, and other related documents, were disposed of immediately after the data analysis was concluded (Maree & Westhuizen, 2007).

To protect the identity of the participants and ensure compliance with the Data Privacy Act of 2012, discrete coding was used to denote each participant's responses. This measure involved carefully phrasing any information that could potentially identify the participants in terms of their name, gender, ethnicity, or employment/location to avoid violating their anonymity. By using proper coding and other measures, the participants' identity was protected, and their privacy was respected.

Justice in the conduct of this study, it was upheld by ensuring that the rights of the participants who identified themselves as English teacher education students were respected. Given that the study aimed to investigate the language exposure and competence of teacher education students, no rights of minor students were violated. To ensure fairness and equal opportunity for participation, the researcher utilized random sampling and purposive sampling techniques. English major teacher education students were not coerced into participating and were given the freedom to decline if they chose. In recognition of their contribution, they were duly credited for their involvement in the research, contributing to the overall success of the study. Additionally, justice was ensured by including only relevant utterances of the participants related to the research objectives and accurately transcribing them (Munhall, 2012; Scott, 2013).

Results and Discussion

This section presents the results of both the quantitative and qualitative phases of the study. The first phase focuses on the quantitative data, displaying the levels of language exposure and language competence among English major students, along with the significant relationships identified. The second phase covers the qualitative data, which is presented through a matrix format. This matrix illustrates participants' responses regarding their lived experiences with language exposure and competence, including their coping mechanisms for challenges faced, and their valuable insights. The matrix also includes the issues investigated, core ideas, codes or categories, essential themes, and the relevant theoretical perspectives. Additionally, another matrix is provided to show the integration of the key findings from both the quantitative and qualitative data.

Level of Language Exposure

Shown in Table 2 is the level of language exposure among English major students in Kapalong Agriculture of Sciences and Technology. It obtained an overall mean score of 3.59 with a descriptive equivalent of High. This means that the English major students manifested oftentimes their language exposure. The variable of the study which is the language exposure which has four indicators namely: home,

friends, school, media.

Home. In terms of home, the category mean is 2.85, which is described as moderate. This means that it is sometimes manifested by the students. Among the items under this indicator, Item No.5 - using English language for specific purposes (e.g., work, studies) got the highest mean of 3.21 with a descriptive equivalent as moderate. This only means it is sometimes manifested by the English major students. Meanwhile, the lowest mean of 2.64 was obtain from item No.2 - conversing with me in English language with descriptive equivalent as moderate which mean it is sometimes manifested by the English major students.

Table 2. *Level of Language Exposure*

<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Description</i>
A. Home		
1. speaking in English usually when having conversations.	2.72	Moderate
2. conversing with me in English language.	2.64	Moderate
3. engaging activities that English language is usually used.	2.81	Moderate
4. speaking English language when there are guests, relatives, or visitors.	2.86	Moderate
5. using English language for specific purposes (e.g., work, studies).	3.21	Moderate
Category Mean	2.85	Moderate
B. Friends		
1. speaking in English language when we conversed.	3.24	Moderate
2. communicating with others in the language of English.	3.31	Moderate
3. attending to social gatherings where English is spoken.	3.26	Moderate
4. expressing preferably in English language when we gather and have fellowship.	3.26	Moderate
5. learning the lesson easily in a collaborative activity in which English is the medium of communication.	3.55	High
Category Mean	3.32	Moderate
C. School		
1. using English language verbally when discussing the lessons particularly my teachers.	4.25	High
2. encouraging the students to speak in English when presenting at the class.	4.25	High
3. using English language as the medium of communication both inside and outside the classroom.	4.00	High
4. speaking verbally in English language when doing homework, projects, or presentations.	4.16	High
5. conducting activities preferably (e.g. presentation, games, etc.) in a form of English language to practice our English language skills.	4.20	High
Category Mean	4.17	High
D. Media		
1. listening to the songs usually in English language.	4.29	Very High
2. chating with my friends online using the English language.	3.56	High
3. reading lots of books or online information on the internet that is written in English language since it is easy for me to understand.	3.96	High
4. browsing online webpages like blog or magazines on the internet that are in English language.	4.01	High
5. watching TV shows and movies in English language.	4.31	Very High
Category Mean	4.03	High

Level of Language Exposure

Friends. In terms of friends, the category mean is 3.32, which is described as moderate. This means that it is sometimes manifested by the students. Among the items under this indicator, Item No.5 - learning the lesson easily in a collaborative activity in which English is the medium of communication got the highest mean of 3.55 with a descriptive equivalent as high. This only means it is oftentimes manifested by the English major students. Meanwhile, the lowest mean of 3.24 was obtain from Item No.1 - speaking in English language when we conversed with descriptive equivalent as moderate which mean it is sometimes manifested by the English major students.

School. In terms of school, the category mean is 4.17, which is described as high. This means that it is oftentimes manifested by the students. Among the items under this indicator, Item No.1 - using English language verbally when discussing the lessons particularly my teachers and Item No.2 - encouraging the students to speak in English when presenting at the class got the highest mean of 4.25 with a descriptive equivalent as high. This only means it is oftentimes manifested by the English major students. Meanwhile, the lowest mean of 4.00 was obtain from Item No.3 - using English language as the medium of communication both inside and outside the classroom with descriptive equivalent as high which mean it is oftentimes manifested by the English major students.

Media. In terms of media, the category mean is 4.03, which is described as high. This means that it is oftentimes manifested by the students. Among the items under this indicator, Item No.5 - conducting activities preferably (e.g. presentation, games, etc.) in a form of English language to practice our English language skills got the highest mean of 4.31 with a descriptive equivalent as very high. This only means it is always manifested by the English major students. Meanwhile, the lowest mean of 3.56 was obtain from Item No.2 - encouraging the students to speak in English when presenting at the class with descriptive equivalent as high which mean it is oftentimes manifested by the English major students.

As to the level of language exposure considering its four indicators, school obtain the highest mean of 4.17 described as high which means it is oftentimes manifested by the English major students. On the other hand, home obtained the lowest overall mean of 2.85 described as moderate which means it is sometimes manifested by the English major students. Then, second highest overall mean of 4.03 was obtained by the indicator media. It has a descriptive equivalent as high which is oftentimes manifested by the English major students. Lastly, it was followed by friends with an overall mean of 3.32 described as moderate which means sometimes manifested by the English major students.

Level of Language Competence

Shown in Table 4 is the level of language competence among English major students in Kapalong Agriculture of Sciences and Technology. It obtained an overall mean score of 3.70 with a description of High. This means that the English major students manifested oftentimes their language exposure. The variable of the study which is the language competence which has five indicators namely: reading, writing, speaking, listening, comprehension.

Reading. In terms of reading, the category mean is 3.69, which is described as high. This means that it is oftentimes manifested by the students. Among the items under this indicator, Item No.5 - reading and understand academic texts in English got the highest mean of 3.82 with a descriptive equivalent as high. This only means it is oftentimes manifested by the English major students. Meanwhile, the lowest mean of 3.64 was obtain from Item No.2 - understanding most of the vocabulary in English texts when reading with descriptive equivalent as high which mean it is oftentimes manifested by the English major students.

Table 2.1. *Level of Language Competence*

<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Description</i>
A. Reading		
	Mean	Description
1. reading English text with no difficulties.	3.66	High
2. understanding most of the vocabulary in English texts.	3.64	High
3. comprehending the nuances and figurative language in English texts when reading.	3.64	High
4. comprehending the main details of a passage in English materials I read.	3.71	High
5. reading and understand academic texts in English.	3.82	High
Category mean	3.69	High
B. Writing		
	Mean	Description
1. writing grammatically correct sentences in English.	3.68	High
2. writing coherently organized paragraphs in English.	3.65	High
3. writing creatively and expressively in English	3.73	High
4. expressing my ideas and thoughts clearly in written English.	3.72	High
5. using grammar and vocabulary effectively in writing English sentences.	3.76	High
Category mean	3.71	High
C. Speaking		
	Mean	Description
1. speaking English fluently and confidently.	3.55	High
2. expressing my ideas and opinions clearly in English.	3.50	High
3. communicating effectively with narrative speakers of English when speaking.	3.58	High
4. using appropriate grammar, vocabulary and pronunciation in English.	3.59	High
5. participating effectively in English discussions and conversations.	3.66	High
Category mean	3.58	High
D. Listening		
	Mean	Description
1. following English conversations and lectures without difficulty.	3.60	High
2. listening for specific details and main ideas in English effectively.	3.66	High
3. listening and comprehending spoken English in a variety of accents and dialects.	3.62	High
4. understanding complex instructions and directions given in English.	3.62	High
5. listening and comprehending different genres of English speech (news, interviews, presentations, etc.)	3.72	High
Category mean	3.64	High
E. Comprehension		
	Mean	Description
1. understanding English language materials related to my academic field.	3.87	High
2. inferring and interpret meaning from English texts.	3.81	High
3. understanding English idioms and figurative languages.	3.72	High
4. using dictionaries and other reference materials to comprehend unfamiliar words in English.	3.97	High
5. using context clues to comprehend unknown words in English.	3.93	High
Category mean	3.86	High

Writing. In terms of writing, the category mean is 3.71, which is described as high. This means that it is oftentimes manifested by the students. Among the items under this indicator, Item No.5 - using grammar and vocabulary effectively in writing English sentences got the highest mean of 3.76 with a descriptive equivalent as high. This only means it is oftentimes manifested by the English major students. Meanwhile, the lowest mean of 3.65 was obtain from Item No.2 - writing coherently organized paragraphs in English with descriptive equivalent as high which mean it is oftentimes manifested by the English major students.

Speaking. In terms of speaking, the category mean is 3.58, which is described as high. This means that it is oftentimes manifested by the students. Among the items under this indicator, Item No.5 - participating effectively in English discussions and conversations got the highest mean of 3.66 with a descriptive equivalent as high. This only means it is oftentimes manifested by the English major students. Meanwhile, the lowest mean of 3.50 was obtain from Item No.2 - expressing my ideas and opinions clearly in English with descriptive equivalent as high which mean it is oftentimes manifested by the English major students.

Listening. In terms of listening, the category mean is 3.64, which is described as high. This means that it is oftentimes manifested by the students. Among the items under this indicator, Item No.5 - listening and comprehending different genres of English speech (news, interviews, presentations, etc.) got the highest mean of 3.72 with a descriptive equivalent as high. This only means it is oftentimes manifested by the English major students. Meanwhile, the lowest mean of 3.60 was obtain from Item No.1 - following English conversations and lectures without difficulty with descriptive equivalent as high which mean it is oftentimes manifested by the English major students.

Comprehension. In terms of comprehension, the category mean is 3.86, which is described as high. This means that it is oftentimes manifested by the students. Among the items under this indicator, Item No.4 - using dictionaries and other reference materials to comprehend unfamiliar words in English got the highest mean of 3.97 with a descriptive equivalent as high. This only means it is oftentimes manifested by the English major students. Meanwhile, the lowest mean of 3.72 was obtain from Item No.3 - understanding English idioms and figurative languages with descriptive equivalent as high which mean it is oftentimes manifested by the English major students.

As to the level of language competence considering its five indicators, comprehension obtain the highest mean of 3.86 described as high which means it is oftentimes manifested by the English major students. On the other hand, speaking obtained the lowest overall mean of 3.58 described as high which means it is oftentimes manifested by the English major students. Then, second highest overall mean of 3.71 was obtained by the indicator writing. It has a descriptive equivalent as high which is oftentimes manifested by the English major students. Then, third highest overall mean was obtained by the indicator reading and it has 3.69 describe as high which means it is oftentimes manifested by the English major students. Lastly, it was followed by listening with an overall mean of 3.64 described as high which means oftentimes manifested by the English major students.

Significant Relationship of Language Exposure and Language Competence

Presented in Table 3 is the result of the significant relationship between language exposure with a mean rating of 3.59 described as high which means that it is oftentimes manifested and language competence with a mean rating of 3.70 described as high which means that it is oftentimes manifested among English major students in Kapalong College of Agriculture, Sciences, and Technology.

Doing an in-depth analysis of the table, the total mean of 3.59 in language exposure and 3.70 in language competence showed a high positive correlation between variables with a total 0.504 R-value which means that there is 50% in the variation of language exposure that affect the language competence of the English major students. While the remaining 50% is the variation not covered in the study.

In addition, result also showed that the P-value of both variable is 0.01 that is less than 0.05 level of significance which means that there is a significant relationship between language exposure and language competence. Hence, this indicated that the null hypothesis which was tested at 0.05 alpha levels was being rejected. To which, the statement that there is no significant relationship between language exposure and language competence English major students in Kapalong College of Agriculture, Sciences, and Technology. To wit, this implied that there is a significant relationship between the two variables which are the language exposure and language competence which was being given evidence according to the result. If the language exposure is good and efficient then the language competence will be similarly good and effective since the independent variable is of a great factor that contributes to the dependent variable.

Table 3. *Significant Relationship of Language Exposure and Language Competence*

<i>Variable</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>R-Value</i>	<i>P-Value</i>	<i>Decision @=0.05</i>
Language Exposure	3.59	.504	<.001	Ho Rejected
Language Competence	3.70			

Lived Experiences and Coping Mechanism of English Major Students with Regards to Language Exposure and Language Competence

Seven essential themes were derived from the in-depth interviews and focus group discussions conducted with the participants regarding the first research question. Prior to presenting the results from these interviews and discussions, Table 3 outlines the profiles of the participants involved in the qualitative data collection.

This table details the participants' profiles, who were selected purposively based on the inclusion criteria: he or she must be a 1st year, 2nd year, 3rd year, or 4th year English major education student in KCAST. Based on the table, the profiles are divided into participants'

sex and year level.

Further, Table 4 deals on the lived experiences and coping mechanisms of the English major students regarding on their language exposure to their language competence. The essential themes which emerged from the transcriptions of the participants’ responses for the research question number one consisted of overarching themes which are summarized in the said table.

Level of Competence with English language used. In the context of language exposure and language competence, some experiences experienced by the students are the developing and moderate level of English language competence as well as average level of English language competence and low level of English language competence. It was mentioned by the participants that each of them has different level of competence when it comes to English language, some are still developing and other considered themselves as average and while some are at low level.

Developing and moderate level of English language Competence. This is the first code of the first probed issue. Some of the participants stated that they are in developing and moderate stage when it comes to the level of their language competence, they seek for improvement in using the language both written and spoken form with a different context.

Similarly, some participants believe that they are the user of English language that is in the developing level. Some of them can comprehend the text or a message properly but in some ways, they are still confused of what is being conveyed. They believed that there are still a room for enhancing English language skills as they believed that it is one of the aspects that creates a barrier in developing language competence. As Participant 1 said that:

“I will describe my competence particularly in English language as developing since I am not that kind of user that is much good at using the language through application. So, I am still learning to enhance my English skill to have my self-manage communication in different context which also contributes to the linguistics demands nowadays.” (IDI-01)

(I would describe my competence in the English language as developing, as I am not yet highly proficient in its practical application. I am still in the process of improving my English skills to better manage communication in various contexts, which is increasingly important given the linguistic demands of today.)

Table 4. *Lived Experiences and coping mechanisms of English major students with regards to language exposure and language competence*

ISSUES PROBED	CORE IDEAS	CODE / CATEGORIES	ESSENTIAL THEME	THEORETICAL SUPPORT
Competence in using the English language	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Having developing level in using the language in different contexts. • Having moderate level for it needs improvement in terms of vocabulary. • Expressing ideas using English both in spoken and written form. 	Developing and moderate level of English language Competence	Level of Competence with English language used	Communicative Competence of Dell Hymes
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • With solid foundation of English language but still needs improvement. • Sharing ideas using simple English words. • Understanding and using English language effectively. 	Average level of English language Competence		
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Feeling scared of using English language in conversations. • Being not able to communicate in straight English. 	Low level of English language Competence		
Language Exposure inside the Classroom	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Speaking English in delivering class reporting. • Establishing rapport with classmates in reporting using English. 	Class Reporting Using English Language	Exposure with Classroom Tasks and Activities	Input Hypothesis of Stephen Krashen
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Being required to use English in oral recitations. • Being required to use English, not vernacular, in recitations. • Speaking English language fluently. 	Participation with Oral Recitations		

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Using English language having teaching demonstration and discussions. Being encouraged to use English in sharing insights in class. 	Engaging in Class Discussion		
Personal Experiences with English Exposure	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Watching different English movies to practice English communication. Opting to watch movies with English subtitles. 	Watching English Movies	Exposure with Media Having English as the Medium	Social Learning Theory of Albert Bandura
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Reading English stories. Engaging various literary texts in literature. Analyzing literary texts. Reading story books given and advise by the teacher. 	Reading and Engaging Various Literary Texts		
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Using English language inside the classroom. Being required to use English in classroom discussion. 	Using English Language in School	Exposure of English Language in Different Contexts	Social Interactionist Theory of Lev Vygotsky
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Using English in posting updates and posts online like in Facebook. Commenting in English online. Reading English memes. 	Using and Reading English Posts and Updates Online		
Positive and Negative Experiences on Language Exposure and Competence	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Lacking vocabulary words in writing essays. Being not able to understand highfalutin words. Having hard time understanding others having difficult words. 	Lack of Vocabulary Knowledge	Deteriorating Knowledge with Lexicon	Interference Theory of Muller and Pilzecker
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Having hard time different rules with grammar. Being not familiar with grammar rules in writing and speaking. 	Difficulty with Grammar Rules	Degrading Interpersonal Skills with English	
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Struggling in understanding slang and informal language. Losing the self-esteem in speaking using English. 	Lack of Self-Confidence in Speaking English		
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Being afraid that the receiver did not fully grasp the thought. Committing language used mistakes and errors which caused confusions. 	Being Misinterpreted by the Receiver		
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Using property the language to connect and relate with people. Broaden the knowledge with the language in apply it in English as a field and specialization. 	Proper Use of the Language		

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Having confidence in speaking and building development with vocabulary. • Learning new words and use it in actual speaking. 	<p>Having Vocabulary Development</p>	<p>Emerging Development with the Language</p>	
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Exposure to diverse forms of English language and develop language competence. • Being able to properly communicate 	<p>Personal Language Development</p>		

Furthermore, Participant believe they are moderate, meaning they can use the language appropriately in specific situations. Despite this, they acknowledge the need to enhance their English vocabulary. This acknowledgment stems from the recognition that English encompasses a vast range of concepts and ideas. By expressing a desire to improve, the speaker demonstrates a proactive attitude towards language learning. As participant 2 said that:

“I would say that I am moderate in terms of using the English language in a way that I could use appropriate language in a specific circumstance but of course I still need to improve my vocabulary in English language because as we all know English la-language covers a wide of concept.” (IDI-02)

(I would consider my proficiency in the English language to be moderate, as I can use appropriate language in specific situations. However, I recognize the need to improve my vocabulary, as the English language encompasses a broad range of concepts.)

Likewise, learners tend to express ideas in English, both in spoken and written form, can significantly enhance your language skills and fluency. This practice can lead to clearer and more effective communication, enabling you to convey complex thoughts and engage in meaningful conversations. This practice exposes you to different styles and forms of the language, broadening your linguistic and cultural knowledge. Overall, regular practice in expressing ideas in English can result in enhanced language exposure. As Participant 4 said that:

“I can communicate my thoughts and ideas clearly, both in writing and speaking.” (IDI-04)

(I am able to communicate my thoughts and ideas clearly, both in writing and in speaking.)

Average level of English language Competence. This is the second code of the first probed issue. The participant considered themselves as an average level when it comes to the use of English language. Participant believed that they have a strong foundation in English, especially because they are English major students. Using simple words in sharing ideas could have a big impact as it ensures clarity and understanding, especially when communicating with diverse audiences. Participant can understand and use English effectively that enables individuals to convey their thoughts and ideas accurately, ensuring that messages are understood by others.

In connection, having a solid foundation in English language exposure can significantly enhance your communication skills, making you more proficient in both written and spoken English. This proficiency can boost your exposure in various social and professional settings, leading to improved relationships and language competence. Having a solid foundation in English language exposure can have far- reaching benefits for your personal and professional development. As Participant 7 said that:

“I would describe my competence in English language as only intermediate or I’m in average because, while I have a solid foundation when it comes to English since first year up to third year I have really solid foundation in English” (FGD-02)

(I would describe my competence in the English language as intermediate or average. I have a solid foundation in English from my first year to my third year of study.)

Also, using simple words in sharing ideas can lead to clearer communication, ensuring that your message is easily understood by a diverse audience. This approach can improve engagement and interest in your ideas, as complex concepts become more accessible and relatable. Additionally, simplifying your language can help you clarify your own thoughts, leading to more effective communication overall. It can also enhance your ability to connect with others, as simple language can bridge gaps in language proficiency or education levels. As participant 8 said that:

“I can understand and communicate and express my ideas using simple words and or basic words lang in English po.” (FGD-03)

(I can understand, communicate, and express my ideas using simple or basic English words.)

In addition, being non-native speaker of the English language can still understand and communicate effectively using the English language. Learners are able to express themselves clearly and confidently in a variety of situations, showing a strong grasp of grammar,

vocabulary, and pronunciation. Participant typically have a deep appreciation for the nuances of the language and can adapt their communication style to suit different contexts and audiences. As Participant 10 said that:

“But somehow we could understand and communicate not so fluently but effectively” (FGD- 05)

(However, we are able to understand and communicate, albeit not fluently, but effectively.)

Low level of English language competence. This is the third code of the first probed. The participants imparted statements that some learners are not able to communicate in straight English and experience a feeling being scared of using English language in conversations. This can be due to a lack of confidence stemming from fear of making mistakes or being judged. This fear can be compounded by past negative experiences or a perceived pressure to speak perfectly. Additionally, limited exposure to English in real-life conversations or environments can hinder language development.

In connection, participant may struggle to communicate in straight English due to a lack of exposure to the language in real-world contexts, limiting their ability to apply what they've learned in the classroom. This lack of practical experience can result in difficulties with fluency and natural expression. Additionally, learners may feel self-conscious about their language skills, leading to a lack of confidence in speaking English because as people see to an English major student are fluent in using the language. As participant 9 said that:

“I tend to have na kanang get scared gihapon kung unsa man akoang ma utter since kanang as an English major students technicality of grammar is really important.” (FGD-04)

(I tend to get scared of what I can utter since that as an English major students technicality of grammar is really important.)

Similarly, it is common for learners to be able to communicate in English but still not feel comfortable engaging in full English conversations. This could be due to a lack of confidence or practice speaking in more complex or spontaneous situations. Some learners may feel more comfortable in structured environments, such as a classroom, where they have more time to think about their responses. As Participant 6 stated that:

“In fact I am able to communicate using the English language yet I’m not that in a level wherein I can engage in English in a full English conversation” (FGD-01)

(In fact, I am able to communicate in English, but I am not yet at a level where I can fully engage in an entire conversation in English.)

Exposure with Classroom Tasks and Activities. In the context of language exposure and language competence, some experiences experienced by the students are class reporting using English language and engaging in class discussion as well as participation with oral recitations. It was mentioned by the participants that there are different task and activities which helps them to be more exposed with the language including class reporting using English language and participation with oral recitations as well as engaging in class discussion.

Class Reporting Using English Language. This is the first code of the second probed issue. Participant recognized class reporting using English language as the task and activities, which helps them to be more exposed with the English language. Participants believe that engaging with this kind of activity can enhance their exposure with the English language.

Similarly, participants believed that the activity of reporting was instrumental in exposing them to the English language. They highlighted that in this activity, they were required to use English for communicating ideas, constructing opinions, and expressing thoughts. This exposure likely helped them become more proficient in English, particularly in terms of speaking and writing skills. It shows that practical, hands-on activities like reporting can significantly contribute to language learning and competence development. As what Participant 2 said that:

“Activity that made me exposed with the English language is reporting because in this activity I am required to use the English language in communicating my idea as well as in constructing my opinions and thoughts.” (IDI-02)

(An activity that has exposed me to the English language is reporting, as it requires me to use English to communicate my ideas and to construct my opinions and thoughts.)

Further, the participants believe that they are exposed to language through activities involving reporting, which can be done either as a group or individually, using English. This indicates that they are engaged in activities that require them to use English for communication. They believe that reporting activities are a common and integral part of their language learning experience. Participants highlights the importance of these activities in enhancing their English language skills and proficiency. As what Participant 3 said that:

“Ang mga activities siguro nga exposed ko sa language kay kanang reporting jud nga kanang by group or individual nga activity nga mag gamit mi ug English” (IDI-03)

(The activities that I am exposed to in terms of language are probably those involving reporting, whether it be done as a group or individually, where we use English.)

Participation with Oral Recitations. This is the second code in the second issues probed. Participant recognized participating in oral recitation using the English language as an activity or task in classroom setting, participant identified this activity as important for improving their English language skills. By actively engaging in oral recitations, they likely expect to improve their English speaking and comprehension skills.

In connection, participant indicates a clear understanding of the role of oral recitations in exposing them to the English language. They acknowledge that being an English major student necessitates frequent use of English, particularly in activities like oral recitations. This suggests that the participant recognizes the importance of practical application in language learning. Additionally, their mention of being an English major student implies a higher level of commitment and proficiency expectation in English. As participant 3 said that:

“Oral recitation pud ma exposed ko dra kay syempre I am English major student so require jud ko mag gamit ug English nga language.” (IDI-03)

(Oral recitation will expose me to the English language because, as an English major student, it is a requirement for me to use English.)

Also, participant recognized on how classroom tasks can help someone get more familiar with the English language. Being a BSED English student, they've taken part in activities like oral recitations, that have exposed them to English. They also recognize that using another language or speaking in vernacular during these activities would naturally push them to use English, thus improving their exposure and practice. This shows that they understand the significance of immersive language experiences and how the context can affect language learning. As Participant 6 said that:

“Classroom activities nga na expose ko sa English language kay oral recitation and presentation like reporting syempre as a BSED English lain pud kayug mo gamit kag lahi nga language or mag vernacular ka syempre maningkamot jud ka na mag use kag English language” (FGD-01)

(As a BSED English student, classroom activities such as oral recitations, presentations, like reporting, exposed me to the English language. Using a different language or speaking vernacular in these activities would naturally prompt the use of English, enhancing exposure and practice.)

In addition, the participant believes that classroom activities, specifically class or oral recitations, have exposed them to the English language. Being encouraged by their instructors to use English when answering questions, highlighting the importance of active language use in learning. Participant views these activities as valuable opportunities to practice and improve their English skills. Additionally, being encouraged by instructors implies a supportive learning environment that promotes language development. This reflects an appreciation for the role of classroom activities in language exposure and skill development. As participant 8 said that:

“Activities such as class or oral recitation as we are encouraged to our instructors to use the language when answering the questions.” (FGD-03)

(Activities such as class discussions or oral recitations encourage us to use the English language when responding to questions posed by our instructors.)

Consequently, participant indicates that as an English major student, they are actively involved in classroom activities that require the use of English, particularly oral recitations. They express a clear understanding of the requirement to speak in English as much as possible. This recognized the importance of consistent language use in enhancing English proficiency. Participant use of the term "intended or involved" suggests a proactive approach to engaging with the language. As Participant 9 said that:

“Oral recitation po since uhm as an English major student we are really require to speak in English as much as possible kanang straight English” (FGD-04)

(Oral recitation since as an English major student we are really required to speak in English as much as possible in straight English.)

Engaging in Class Discussion. This is the third code of the second issues probed. Participant recognized engaging in class discussion using the English language as an activity or task in classroom setting, participant recognized this activity as significant for enhancing their exposure in the English language. Hence, class discussions are essential for creating a dynamic language learning environment that fosters comprehensive language exposure and competence development.

In connection, participants indicate a comfort and proficiency in using English for formal communication purposes. Learners implies a recognition of the importance of English in their academic or professional context. The use of "we also tend to like" suggests that this preference is shared among their peers or group members. This collective preference may be influenced by the educational environment or cultural factors that emphasize the importance of English proficiency. It reflects a proactive approach to using English for formal communication, possibly driven by its perceived advantages and the norms of their environment. As Participant 9 said that:

“Let say demonstration po wherein we also tend to like deliver our reports or discussions po through English language” (FGD-04)

(For instance, during demonstrations, we often deliver our reports or discussions in English.)

In addition, participant response indicates that they primarily experience exposure to the English language through classroom discussions. They perceive classroom discussions as a common activity that exposes them to English regularly. The participant's exposure to English is structured and intentional, as it is a requirement in these activities. It implies that this exposure has influenced their language use, as they tend to speak English as a result. As per Participant 10 said that:

“Activities that been made exposed to English language is the classroom discussion for me that is the common thing that I am being exposed to the language and as well as uhm the oral recitation where as we are being encourage or uhm oblige to talk in English in sharing ideas so that’s why uhm we tend to speak in English” (FGD-05).

(The activities that have exposed me to the English language include classroom discussions, which are a common occurrence and provide regular exposure to the language. Additionally, oral recitations require us to share ideas in English, as we are encouraged or obligated to do so, leading to a tendency to speak English.)

Exposure with Media Having English as the Medium. In the context of language exposure and language competence, some experiences experienced by the students are watching English movies and reading and engaging various literary texts. It was mentioned by the participants that they become exposed with the English language through media including watching English movies and reading and engaging various literary texts.

Watching English Movies. This is the first code of the third issues probed. Students reported that they watch different English movies to practice English communication. Regularly watching English movies can be a fun and effective way to enhance language exposure and improve communication skills. Also, they choose to watch movies with English subtitles as it can expose you to different accents and dialects, helping you become more familiar with the diversity of the English language.

Similarly, learners highlighted that they have actively engaged with the English language through watching movies. They view this activity as a means of exposure that has allowed them to practice and enhance their English communication skills. They acknowledge the role of movies in providing opportunities for practice, indicating a proactive approach to language learning. Learners reflects a positive attitude towards using movies as a tool for language exposure and skill development. As Participant 5 said that:

“So, my personal experiences po that I am exposed to English language is that through watching movies nga English ang kanang language nga ginagamit para ma practice nako ang pag gamit sa English in terms of communicating.” (IDI-05)

(My personal experience, I have been exposed to the English language through the use of English in movies, which has provided me with opportunities to practice and improve my English communication skills.)

Also, the participant believed that they find value in watching English movies with subtitles as a way to enhance their reading skills. They enjoy this activity because it allows them to practice reading while simultaneously understanding the movie's dialogue. This indicates a proactive approach to language learning, as they use movies as a tool for skill development. This implies a positive attitude towards this practice, which can enhance their motivation to learn. Also, learners highlights the benefits of using subtitles to improve reading comprehension and language proficiency. As Participant 9 said that:

“I tend to like uhm watch English movies with subtitle so that I could read subtitles and by that murag ma practice akoang reading skills which is also gina comprehend pud nako ug unsa akong na basa” (FGD-04)

(I enjoy watching English movies with subtitles because it helps me practice my reading skills. This way, I can understand and comprehend the subtitles while watching the movie.)

Reading and Engaging Various Literary Texts. This is the second code of the third issues probed. This helps you understand cultural nuances and contexts, contributing to a deeper understanding and appreciation of the English language. Literary texts often contain complex sentence structures and grammatical patterns, providing valuable examples for language learners to study and emulate. reading such texts exposes learners to different writing styles, enriching their understanding of the language's nuances. Moreover, analyzing and discussing these texts can improve critical thinking skills and the ability to express ideas effectively in English.

In connection, the participant report that they were exposed to English stories, which they read in their free time. This suggests a proactive approach to language exposure and learning. They imply that this activity is shared among a group, possibly indicating a cultural or educational context where reading English stories is encouraged. Reading English stories is a regular and habitual activity for them, which can contribute significantly to their language proficiency and become more exposed with the language. As participant 6 said that:

“Gi expose mi sapag basa og English stories, so every naa mi free time naga, basa mig English stories” (FGD-01)

(We were exposed to reading English stories, so every time we have free time we read English stories.)

Moreover, learners indicates that they actively interact with a variety of literary texts, particularly in a literature-focused subject. This suggests a high level of involvement and interest in literature. They recognize a deep and meaningful interaction with the texts, rather than passive reading. Their exposure to literary texts is intentional and structured, likely contributing significantly to their understanding and appreciation of literature. Participants response reflects a strong commitment to engaging with literary texts as part of their

academic pursuit. As participant 7 said that:

“I engage with various literary texts specially sa amoang subject is all about literature.” (FGD-02)

(I engage with various literary texts especially in our subject which is all about literature.)

Also, learners believe that they were exposed to the English language through the analysis of literature. This indicates that their exposure to English was likely through academic or literary studies, where they engaged deeply with English texts. The term analyze implies a thorough and critical examination of literature, suggesting a high level of language immersion and comprehension. Their statement also implies that this exposure was intentional, indicating a deliberate effort to study and understand English literature. Participants response reflects a structured and academic approach to language exposure and learning. As Participant 9 said that:

“I got expose to English language we tend to like analyze a lot of literature po” (FGD-09)

(I got exposed to English language when we tend to like analyze a lot of literature.)

Furthermore, participants indicates that they were exposed to the English language through classroom activities involving reading storybooks. They believe that their exposure to English was facilitated by their teachers reading storybooks aloud in the classroom. Learners implies a passive reception of the language, indicating that this exposure was part of their regular classroom experience. This indicates that their exposure to English was likely interactive and engaging, which can enhance language acquisition. Participants highlights the role of classroom activities and teacher-led reading in facilitating language exposure and learning. As Participant 5 said that:

“Classroom activities naman that made me exposed to the English language is kanang through reading story books nga gina pabasa sa teachers sa classroom” (IDI-05)

(Classroom activities that made me exposed to the English language is through reading story books that the teachers read in the classroom.)

Exposure of English Language in Different Contexts. In the context of language exposure, some experiences experienced by the students are using English language in school and using and reading English posts and updates online. It was mentioned by the participants that they become exposed with the English language through using the language in school setting and reading English post and updates online.

Using English Language in School. This is the third code of the third issues probed. It provides a structured environment for practicing and using English regularly, which is crucial for language acquisition. Also, it exposes learners to a variety of English accents, vocabulary, and expressions used by teachers and classmates. Additionally, using English in school facilitates participation in classroom discussions, presentations, and activities, promoting active language use and skill development. Furthermore, it helps learners become more comfortable and confident in using English in various contexts, both inside and outside the classroom.

In connection, the participants indicates that in the classroom, they are obligated to use the English language. This also indicates that their exposure to English is a formal requirement of their academic environment. They believe that the use of English is mandatory, possibly indicating that they are in an English-speaking or bilingual educational setting. Their statement also implies that this requirement is consistent and applies to various classroom activities and interactions. The participant recognizes the importance of using English in their academic context and is compliant with this requirement. As Participant 2 said that:

“In the classroom I am required to use the English language” (IDI-02)

(In the classroom, I am required to use the English language.)

Also, participant's response indicates that they are required to use the English language, particularly in the classroom setting. This suggests that their exposure to English is structured and mandatory within the school environment. It implies that the use of English is a formal rule or standard during discussions, indicating a consistent and enforced language policy. Also, the use of English is a norm or expectation in their academic setting, suggesting that it is the primary language of instruction. Additionally, participant recognizes the importance of using English in their academic context and adheres to this requirement. As Participant 2 said that:

“When it comes to the use of English language uhm inside the school specially in the classroom I am required to use the English language or mag ruling or kanang mao ang ginagamit during discussion” (IDI- 02)

(When it comes to the use of English language uhm inside the school especially in the classroom I am required to use the English language or rule or that is what is used during discussion.)

Using and Reading English Posts and Updates Online. This is the fourth code of the third issues probed. Using and reading English posts and updates online can significantly contribute to English language exposure. Online platforms offer a vast array of written and multimedia content in English, providing constant exposure to the language. By engaging with these posts and updates, individuals encounter a variety of linguistic features, which can enhance their language proficiency. Engaging with English posts and updates online is an effective and accessible way to immerse oneself in the language and improve language competence.

In connection, the participant's response indicates that they use English when posting online and read a lot of posts in English. This suggests that their exposure to English is a result of their online activities, where they actively use and encounter the language. There are instances that their use of English is not constant but occurs regularly enough to contribute to their language exposure. Additionally, it implies that their exposure to English is varied, as they encounter different styles and forms of English in online posts. Overall, their response reflects a practical and effective method of language exposure through online interactions. As Participant 1 said that:

“Kay usahay gagamit man kog English kung mag post ko sa Facebook and daghan pud kog mabasahan nga mga post nga gagamit ug English” (IDI-01)

(Because sometimes I use English when I post on Facebook and I also read a lot of posts that use English.)

In addition, participants report that they use English in a casual and informal manner, such as when commenting on posts online. This implies that their use of English is not formal or structured but rather spontaneous and relaxed. Also, it indicates that their English use is likely in a social media or online context, where interactions are often informal and conversational. This implies a level of comfort and familiarity with using English in informal settings. Additionally, their use of English in online comments may indicate a desire to connect with others or engage in discussions in English-speaking communities. Participant 4 stated that:

“I use English in a relaxed way, like commenting on posts” (IDI-04)

(I use English in a casual manner, such as when commenting on posts.)

Also, participant's response indicates that they engage with memes that use English, suggesting that they are exposed to informal English language content online. Analyzing memes correctly implies a level of attention to detail and understanding of the nuances of English used in this type of content. The participant sees value in accurately interpreting and understanding the English language, even in informal contexts. This reflects a casual yet attentive approach to using and understanding English in online contexts. As Participant 5 said that:

“Also kanang sa mga memes nga akong mabasa tas need sya -ianalyze ug tarong gani since English man iyang ginagamit”. (IDI-05)

(Also, those memes that I read, it needs to be analyzed correctly since English language was used)

Deteriorating Knowledge with Lexicon. In the context of language exposure and competence, some experiences experienced by the students are lack of vocabulary knowledge and difficulty with grammar rules. It was mentioned by the participants that they face these challenges with regards to the exposure of the English language and enhancing the level of competence with use English language.

Lack of Vocabulary Knowledge. This is the first code of the fourth issues probed. The lack of vocabulary knowledge can significantly impact various aspects of language use. It may result in difficulties when writing essays, as individuals may struggle to find appropriate words to express their ideas clearly and effectively. Additionally, not understanding highfalutin words can hinder comprehension, especially when reading complex texts or engaging in academic or professional discussions. Lastly, individuals may have a hard time understanding others who use difficult words, leading to challenges in communication and learning.

In connection with, participant's response suggests that their exposure to the English language may be limited by a lack of vocabulary, particularly in certain forms of communication or writing. This implies that they encounter difficulties expressing themselves or understanding others due to a limited range of words. The use of "maybe" indicates a degree of uncertainty regarding the impact of their vocabulary limitations on their language exposure. Their statement reflects an awareness of their vocabulary challenges and how these challenges may affect their language use and comprehension. Participant 1 stated that:

“With regards to my exposure with the use of English language is maybe kana ganing lack of vocabulary na akong ma experience through the certain communication or writing” (IDI-01)

(With regards to my exposure with the use of English language is maybe that lack of vocabulary that I experience through the certain communication or writing.)

Also, the participants admit that they face difficulties when exposed to the English language, particularly in academic contexts or classrooms, when teachers or classmates use highfalutin words. Encountering complex or unfamiliar vocabulary presents a challenge for them in understanding and engaging with the language. This implies that these challenges are significant and impactful. This reflects a specific context where they experience these difficulties, highlighting the importance of context in language learning. Additionally, the participant is aware of the impact of highfalutin words on their language comprehension and may seek strategies to address this challenge. As participant 7 said that:

“Difficulties that I've faced when I am exposed to the English language is in academic context or in a classroom, when teachers or my classmates use high falutin words” (FGD-02)

(The difficulties I encounter when exposed to the English language occur in academic contexts or in the classroom, particularly when teachers or classmates use complex or advanced vocabulary.)

Consequently, the participants reveal that they face challenges when someone uses complex or unfamiliar words while speaking to

them. They may struggle with comprehension or understanding in such situations. This implies that this is a significant issue for them in their language learning or communication experiences. Their statement reflects a specific scenario where they encounter these challenges, highlighting the impact of unfamiliar vocabulary on their ability to understand spoken English. Additionally, the participant is aware of the importance of clear and understandable language in effective communication. As participant 8 said that:

“The main challenges that I’ve usually encounter is when kana bitawng naa koy ka storya nya gagamit syag laglom nga mga words nya dili nimo ma sabtan” (FDG-03)

(The main challenges that I've usually encounter is when someone is talking to me and he/she uses deep words that you don't understand.)

Difficulty with Grammar Rules. This is the second code of the fourth issues probed. Difficulty with grammar rules can impede both writing and speaking proficiency. Individuals may struggle to differentiate between various grammar rules, leading to errors in usage. Additionally, unfamiliarity with grammar rules can hinder effective communication, as individuals may be unsure of how to structure sentences correctly.

In connection, the participants reveals that they feel less confident or proficient in using English grammar rules. Their response implies a comparative assessment, indicating that they perceive a gap in their grammar proficiency compared to other aspects of language use. Their statement indicates a specific focus on grammar rules, suggesting that they may find this aspect of English language usage particularly challenging. Learners’ response reflects a self-assessment of their grammar skills, indicating a level of awareness of their strengths and weaknesses in English language usage. As participant 5 said that:

“When it comes to usage in English language like ang kanang sa grammar, dili pajod kaayu ko as in kanang fluent when it comes sa kanang sa grammar rules” (IDI-05)

(When it comes to usage in English language particularly in grammar, I am not as fluent when it comes to grammar rules.)

Also, participant's response indicates that they are not familiar with all grammar rules, suggesting a lack of comprehensive knowledge in this area, they may struggle to identify or apply grammar rules, both in writing and spoken language. They may feel overwhelmed or uncertain when faced with the task of identifying grammar rules. Additionally, their grammar challenges extend to various forms of communication. Overall, their response reflects a sense of limitation or difficulty in applying grammar rules, indicating a potential area for improvement in their language skills. As Participant 6 said that:

“Dili tanan grammar rules is familiar ko and if naa koy kanang ipa identify sakoa ang grammar rule is kanang mawala ko or maglisod jud ko both writing man or spoken” (FGD-01)

(I am not familiar with all grammar rules, and if I have to identify a specific grammar rule, I may struggle or encounter difficulty, whether in writing or speaking.)

Degrading Interpersonal Skills with English. In the context of language exposure and competence, some experiences experienced by the students are lack of self-confidence in speaking English and being misinterpreted by the receiver. It was mentioned by the participants that they face these challenges with regards to the exposure of the English language and enhancing the level of competence with use English language.

Lack of Self-Confidence in Speaking English. This is the third code of the fourth issues probed. Lack of self-confidence in speaking English can stem from various factors, including difficulties in understanding slang and informal language. This can lead to a loss of self-esteem when using English, particularly in casual or informal settings. The use of slang and informal language can present challenges for language learners, as it may not be taught in formal language courses. Lastly, a lack of self-confidence in speaking English can hinder effective communication and limit opportunities for language practice and improvement.

In connection, the participants acknowledge having difficulty understanding slang and informal language. They may find colloquial expressions or informal speech patterns challenging to comprehend. Their statement reflects a specific area of difficulty within the broader context of English language comprehension. Additionally, they may need additional exposure or practice to become more comfortable with slang and informal language. Participants highlights a specific language challenge and indicates a potential area for improvement in their language skills. As Participant 4 said that:

“I struggle in understanding slang and informal language” (IDI-04)

(I find it difficult to comprehend slang and informal language.)

In addition, the participants believed that they struggle with speaking confidently, especially in front of others, when using English. This suggests that they may experience anxiety or self-doubt when speaking English in social or public settings. This implies that this issue has a significant impact on their ability to communicate effectively in English. Participants statements reflect a specific challenge related to speaking confidence within the broader context of language proficiency. Additionally, they are aware of this challenge and its impact on their language skills. Overall, their responses highlight a specific area for improvement in their English language proficiency and indicate a need for strategies to build speaking confidence. As participant 4:

“Another difficulty is that speaking confidently, especially in front of others.” (IDI-04)

(Another difficulty is speaking confidently, particularly when addressing others.)

Being Misinterpreted by the Receiver. This is the fourth code of the fourth issues probed. Being misinterpreted by the receiver can lead to feelings of uncertainty and fear that the intended message was not fully understood. The fear of being misunderstood can create barriers to effective communication and hinder the conveyance of ideas accurately. The possibility of being misinterpreted highlights the importance of clear and precise language use in effective communication.

In connection with, the participant's response indicates a lack of confidence in their ability to communicate clearly in English. They express hesitation to communicate because they are unsure if the receiver will fully understand their message. This suggests a fear of being misunderstood or not being able to express themselves effectively. The use of "even hesitate" emphasizes the extent of their uncertainty. Their statement reflects a concern about the potential for miscommunication, highlighting the importance of clarity in communication. Overall, their response underscores the impact of language barriers on their confidence and willingness to communicate in English. As Participant 2 said that:

“Mag duha2 gani kog communicate sa language since I wouldn't know if the receiver of my message will completely understand what I am talking” (IDI-02)

(I even hesitate to communicate in language since I wouldn't know if the receiver of my message will completely understand what I am talking about.)

In addition, participants response recognize frustration when they are unable to understand something or when they make mistakes. This suggests a level of self- awareness regarding their language learning process and the challenges they face. This conveys a strong emotional response, highlighting the impact of these difficulties on their learning experience. This reflects a common experience among language learners, as the process of learning a new language can be challenging and frustrating at times. Their response underscores the emotional aspect of language learning and the importance of perseverance in overcoming obstacles. As Participant 4 said that:

“I am feeling frustrated when I can't understand something or when I make mistake” (IDI-04)

(I become frustrated when I don't understand something or when I make a mistake.)

Proper Use of the Language. This is the fifth code of the fourth issues probed. The use of language is essential for connecting and relating to people effectively. It broadens knowledge and understanding, especially when applied in specialized fields like English. Proper language use not only facilitates communication but also enhances learning and professional development. It enables individuals to express ideas clearly and accurately, fostering better understanding and collaboration. Moreover, using language appropriately demonstrates respect for cultural and linguistic diversity.

In connection, the learners believe proper use of language is important for connecting with people. They express a desire to understand how words should be used in different circumstances to facilitate meaningful connections. This implies a hypothetical situation, indicating that they may feel limited in their current ability to use language effectively. Their statement reflects a recognition of the importance of language in communication and relationship-building. Additionally, their response highlights a desire for proficiency in language use to facilitate meaningful connections. As Participant 2 said that:

“I could use the language properly, I would know or how these words should be used in certain circumstances for me to be able to really connect with people” (IDI-02)

(If I could use the language properly, I would know how to use these words in specific circumstances, enabling me to effectively connect with people.)

Also, the participants believe that they have expanded their understanding of English and have applied it to their major field of study. This implies a proactive effort to learn and improve their English skills. Their statement reflects a connection between their English language proficiency and its practical application in their academic pursuits. Additionally, they recognized the relevance of English language skills to their major which is English. Overall, their response indicates a positive attitude towards language learning and its integration into their academic endeavors, despite the grammatical error. As Participant 6 said that:

“I broadened my knowledge of English and applied I apply it to my major.” (FGD-01)

(I expanded my knowledge of English and applied it to my major.)

Having Vocabulary Development. This is the sixth code of the fourth issues probed. Vocabulary development is essential for building confidence in speaking and expanding one's word repertoire. Learning new words and using them in actual conversations helps reinforce their usage and improves language skills. This process enhances communication abilities and allows individuals to express themselves more effectively. Overall, developing a strong vocabulary is key to improving speaking confidence and language proficiency.

In connection, participant reveal that they experienced an increase in confidence in speaking and understanding English. Also, they

feel more comfortable and proficient in using the language. Their response implies that they have actively learned new words, which has enriched their language skills. Their statement also suggests that they can now communicate effectively in English, indicating a positive outcome from their language learning efforts. This reflects a positive impact on their language skills and confidence, highlighting the benefits of language development. As Participant 5 said that:

“Na increase akong confidence in speaking and understanding in English, na extend niya akong vocabulary tapos I am able to communicate effectively using the English language” (IDI-05)

(It increased my confidence in speaking and understanding English, expanded my vocabulary, and enabled me to communicate effectively in the English language.)

Also, the participants recognize perceive learning new words and effective communication in English as positive experiences. They indicate that learning new words enhances their vocabulary, which may contribute to their overall language proficiency. Additionally, participant highlight the importance of effective communication in English, indicating that they value the ability to convey their thoughts and ideas accurately. Their statement reflects a proactive approach to language learning, as they actively seek to expand their vocabulary to improve their communication skills. As Participant 3 said that:

“When I learn new words and ako syang magamit in actual” (IDI-03)

(When I learn new words and get to use them in actual situations.)

Personal Language Development. This is the seventh code of the fourth issues probed. Personal language development involves exposure to diverse forms of the English language, which helps in developing language competence. It also includes the ability to communicate effectively with others using English. Exposure to different forms of English, such as through media or interactions with speakers of different dialects, can enhance language skills and understanding. Effective communication involves not just vocabulary and grammar but also the ability to convey ideas clearly and appropriately.

In relation, the participants believe that they have had positive experiences in improving their English language skills through exposure to diverse forms of English. Their statement reflects a proactive approach to language learning, as they actively seek out diverse forms of English to enhance their skills. Additionally, they value the importance of exposure in language development. Participants response highlights the positive impact of exposure to diverse forms of English on their language skills and development. As Participant 7 said that:

“The positive experiences in relation to my English language exposure, includes improving my language skills through exposure to diverse forms of English” (FGD-02)

(The positive experiences related to my exposure to the English language include improving my language skills through engagement with various forms of English.)

Also, the participants report that they are able to communicate effectively in English. They believe that they can convey their thoughts and ideas accurately and appropriately in English. Their statement reflects a positive assessment of their language ability, indicating that they consider themselves to be successful communicators in English. Participants response highlights their confidence and proficiency in using the English language for communication. As Participant 8 said that:

“I able to communicate properly using the English language” (FGD-03)

(I am able to communicate effectively using the English language.)

Insights Shared of English Major Students with Regards to Language Exposure and Language Competence

Displayed in Table 4.2 are the responses of the participants in regards to their insight in language exposure and language competence. There are six essential themes which are drawn out from the in-depth and focus group discussion of the participants for the second question. The essential themes consisted codes based from the issues being probed which are summarized in the table.

Constant Practice with the Language and Be Open with Feedback. The insight of the English education students in accordance with their language exposure and competence are being affected based from the responses given by the participants.

Based on the information given by the participants, it is claimed that because of constant practice with the language and be open with feedback they can develop one’s language exposure and competence.

Being open to feedback and criticism. This is the first code of the first issues probed. When students commit mistakes or error, students can enhance their skills by being open to feedback and criticism.

Students should accept comments from teachers, stay motivated, and provide feedback to others, which helps create a supportive learning environment. These actions not only improve individual language skills but also contribute to a collaborative and effective learning atmosphere.

Table 4.2. Insights of English major students with regards to language exposure and language competence

ISSUES PROBED	CORE IDEAS	CODE / CATEGORIES	ESSENTIAL THEME	THEORETICAL SUPPORT
Advise and Recommendations for Teachers and Students in developing One's Language Exposure and Competence	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Being open to hear constructive feedback and criticism from teachers. • Being positive in accepting feedback from instructors to be guided on their mistakes committed. • Accepting the comments of the teacher and stay motivated in class. • Providing feedback for students coming from teachers letting their students know about their linguistic mistake and error. 	Being Open to Feedback and Criticism	Constant Practice with the Language and Be Open with Feedback	Skills Acquisition Theory of Robert DeKeyser
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Consistent reading with various books having different genres and styles. • Reading books to discover new terms and words which will enhance students' vocabulary. • Reading different books and articles which is interesting as its students different learning styles and enrich their linguistic vocabulary. 	Making Reading a Habit		
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Using English in talking and communicating with others to enhance one's language competence. • Utilizing English in daily conversations if possible and if they can. • Having English in different conversations to allow themselves to learn new vocabularies. 	Using English in Daily Lives		
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Immersing oneself with various inputs and learning materials using the English language to likewise learn the language. • Reading different books and language learning materials and articles to develops one's vocabulary and develop language used and styles. 	Exposure with Diverse Learning Materials	One Must Have Exposure with Varied Language Activities and Resources	
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Practicing writing essays and short stories to help students express themselves through writing. • Seeking opportunities outside the classroom like joining English clubs. • Seeking participating in the different learning activities like debate, and discussion for them to be active in developing their language competence. 	Participation with School Activities		

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Employing engaging activities like speech and stage play, radio broadcasting, and role play to engage more the students. • Incorporating varieties of activities to develop one's language competence like interactive games. • Using interactive activities where students and teachers will be exposed with the language. 	Employ Engaging Activities and Discussion	Essential of Employing Engaging Activities to Engage Students	Experiential Learning Theory of David Kolb
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Having meaningful discussions making the students be exposed with the English language. 		

Similarly, the participant's response aligns with the importance of being open to constructive feedback and criticism from teachers, a key aspect of language development. By emphasizing the value of seeking feedback constructively, it encourages students to view feedback as a tool for improvement, reflecting a growth mindset. Such openness to feedback can enhance students' language competence and overall learning experience. The participants provide a practical strategy for students to develop their language skills effectively. As Participant 9 said that:

“I can share to all other English major students for them to develop their language competence if kanang they tend to be open sa kanang learning the English language kumbaga they to like see feedback or kanang criticism to teachers in such way nga constructively na they use it as a stepping stone ba to be good in English language.” (FGD-04)

(I can share with other English major students to help them develop their language competence. They should be open to learning the English language, seeking feedback and criticism from teachers constructively and using it as a stepping stone to improve their English proficiency.)

Moreover, the students recognized the importance of accepting corrections and feedback from instructors as a valuable learning opportunity. By acknowledging the guidance provided by instructors, students can actively address their mistakes and improve their language skills. This approach fosters a supportive learning environment where feedback is seen as a means for growth. The participants highlight the role of feedback in enhancing language competence among students. As Participant 10 said that:

“As well as accepting those corrections and feedback provided by the instructors so that you are being guided to every mistakes you did” (FGD-05)

(Additionally, accepting corrections and feedback from instructors helps ensure that you are guided through each mistake you make.)

In addition, the participants acknowledge the importance of providing constructive feedback to students to maintain their motivation in developing their language competence. By recognizing the role of feedback in motivation, educators can create a supportive environment conducive to language development. This approach encourages students to view feedback as a tool for improvement rather than criticism, fostering a growth mindset. The learner's insight underscores the significance of constructive feedback in enhancing students' language competence and motivation. As Participant 6 said that:

“Provide constructive feedback with students' performance para ang mga students is stay motivated sila sailahang pag develop sailahang language competence.” (FGD-01)

(Provide constructive feedback on students' performance so that they stay motivated in their language competence development.)

Furthermore, the students recognize the importance of consistent feedback from teachers in helping students identify mistakes and improve. By providing constructive feedback, teachers not only help students improve their language skills but also expose them to the English language and letting the students know their mistakes and improve it. The participant's perspective emphasizes the positive impact of feedback on students' language competence and exposure to English. As Participant 8 said that:

“Also the teacher must always give ah feedback about their competence so that ahh students will able to know kung asa sila mali ang they could improve it and para pud ma expose sila sa English language” (FGD-03)

(The teacher must consistently provide feedback on students' competence so that students can identify their mistakes and areas for improvement. This process also helps expose them to the English language.)

Making Reading a Habit. This is the second code of the first issues probed. This contributes to developing language exposure and competence by immersing oneself in English books. This exposure allows students to encounter a wide range of vocabulary and language structures, enhancing their language skills. Consistent reading also improves comprehension and language knowledge,

leading to greater proficiency in using the language. This is a valuable strategy for developing language competence and exposure.

With regards to that, the participants emphasize the importance of reading English books in developing language competence among English major students. By encouraging students to read English books, students can promote language exposure and vocabulary. This practice also helps students become more familiar with English sentence structures and writing styles. As Participant 2 said that:

“The only thing that I could really share to other English major students for them to really develop their language competence is to read English books in which in this book they will be able to discover new terms, discover new words in which it will enhance their vocabulary.” (IDI-02)

(The primary advice I would offer to other English major students for developing their language competence is to read English books. Through these books, they can discover new terms and expand their vocabulary.)

Moreover, the students believe to the effectiveness of consistent reading in enhancing language competence, particularly when exploring various genres and styles. By diversifying their reading materials, students can expose themselves to different vocabulary and language structures, which can improve their language skills. This also helps students become more proficient in understanding different writing styles and contexts. It underscores the importance of regular and diverse reading in developing language competence among students. As Participant 7 said that:

“One effective way to enhance language competence is through consistent reading, especially of diverse genres and styles.” (FGD-02)

(One effective method for enhancing language competence is through consistent reading, particularly across a variety of genres and styles.)

Furthermore, participant believe that reading books and articles can be beneficial for improving vocabulary and language skills. Students can take this advice as a recommendation to actively read and explore various written resources in English to enhance their language proficiency. Additionally, it highlights the importance of continuous reading to strengthen vocabulary and language usage. As Participant 3 said that:

“Like mag read tag books, or any articles nga makatabang sa ato sa pag develop sa atong vocabulary and sa pag gamit sa language” (IDI-03)

(Reading books or any articles that can help us develop our vocabulary and language use.)

Using English in Daily Lives. This is the third code of the first issues probed. Using English in daily conversations can significantly enhance one's language competence. By actively incorporating English into everyday interactions, individuals can improve their vocabulary and communication skills. It is beneficial to engage in diverse conversations in English to learn new words and phrases. Consistent use of English in daily life helps build confidence and fluency in the language. Integrating English into daily routines is key to developing language proficiency.

Similarly, the participants believe that students should actively use the language in their daily lives to enhance their language competence. By engaging in daily communication, students can develop the ability to use the language effectively in various contexts. This practice not only improves their language skills but also boosts their confidence in using the language. Encouraging students to apply their language skills in everyday situations can lead to a deeper understanding and mastery of the language. As Participant 2 said that:

“They should use the language through everyday use because through using the language everyday they would develop the capacity to really use the language in everyday communication because I believe through talking or through really using the language in everyday communication it will really enhance their language competence.” (IDI_02)

(They should use the language daily because this practice helps develop the capacity to communicate effectively in daily interactions. I believe that frequent use of the language in everyday conversations enhances language competence.)

Moreover, the participant emphasizes the importance of daily English language use for enhancing language competence. This underscores the practical aspect of language learning, advocating for active engagement in daily conversations to improve language skills. Implementing this advice could lead to significant improvements in students' language competence, especially when combined with formal instruction. As Participant 5 said that:

“For them to develop their language competence kanang they should use English language in their daily communication if makaya nila, if pwede lang.” (IDI-05)

(For them to develop their language competence, they should use the English language in their daily communication if they are able to, if it is possible.)

Furthermore, the learners believes that regular English conversations and actively learning and using new words and phrases are key to improving language skills. It also implies that students should be proactive in seeking opportunities to use English, indicating a proactive approach to learning. The participant emphasizes the importance of practical application and continuous learning in language

proficiency. As Participant 3 said that:

“They should really use the language daily for them to become good in communicating with the use of English language and at least they should also at least learn new words to expand their vocabulary.” (FGD-03)

(To further enhance their language skills, they should engage in regular conversations using English and actively seek out opportunities to learn and apply new words and phrases in their daily interactions.)

One Must Have Exposure with Varied Language Activities and Resources. Exposure to a variety of language activities and resources is essential for language development. This includes engaging with diverse learning materials and participating in school activities that promote language use. Such exposure provides opportunities to practice and improve language skills in different contexts. Active participation in these activities enhances language competence and allows learners to apply their skills in real-world situations.

Exposure with Diverse Learning Materials. This is the third code of the first issues probed. Exposure to diverse learning materials is essential for language development. Immersing students in diverse inputs and materials in English can greatly aid in their language learning process. Encouraging students to read different books, articles, and language learning materials helps them develop their vocabulary and understand different language styles. This exposure is vital for students to improve their language competence and effectively communicate in English.

With regards to that, participants believe that students can benefit from immersing themselves in diverse English language materials to enhance their learning. It implies that exposure to a variety of English resources can greatly aid in language acquisition. In addition, the participants' response highlights the significance of immersion in diverse English materials as a strategy for language learning. As Participant 1 said that:

“Kuan siguro, immerse themselves with various input or material that is related to the context of English language because it helps them a lot to acquire or learn the specific language” (IDI-01)

(Perhaps, they should immerse themselves in various inputs or materials related to the context of the English language because it greatly aids in acquiring or learning the specific language.)

In addition, the students emphasize the importance of extensive reading for English majors, suggesting that they should read books, articles, and other materials of interest. Engaging in extensive reading can expand vocabulary and expose students to various writing styles, enhancing their language skills. Furthermore, it encourages students to explore different genres and styles, contributing to a deeper understanding of language use. It highlights the importance of reading for English majors to enhance their language skills and writing ability. As Participant 4 said that:

“One thing that I can really suggest to other English major is to read a lot. So, books, articles, or anything you find interesting because when you read a lot it helps expand your vocabulary and gives you different writing styles to learn from.” (IDI_04)

(One valuable suggestion I can offer to other English majors is to engage in extensive reading of books, articles, or any materials that interest them. Reading helps expand vocabulary and exposes individuals to various writing styles, facilitating learning.)

Participation with School Activities. This is the fifth code of the first issues probed. Participating in school activities can significantly contribute to students' language development. Engaging in activities such as writing essays and short stories helps students express themselves effectively in writing. Additionally, seeking opportunities beyond the classroom, like joining English clubs, provides a platform for continuous language practice and improvement. Moreover, actively participating in various learning activities such as debates and discussions allows students to be more proactive in honing their language skills.

Similarly, the students emphasize the importance of regular writing practice, suggesting that activities like journaling, essay writing, and storytelling can improve one's ability to express themselves. The participant highlights the value of writing in enhancing self-expression, implying that consistent writing exercises can lead to more effective communication skills. As Participant 4 said that:

“And also, you should practice writing regularly, it could be journaling or writing essays, or even writing short stories. So, kuan, writing a lot I can really help you express yourself better” (IDI-04)

(And also, you should practice writing regularly, whether it's journaling, writing essays, or even crafting short stories. Writing can significantly help you express yourself more effectively.)

In addition, the participant recognizes the importance of seeking opportunities beyond formal classroom settings to enhance their language exposure. They believe that joining English clubs can provide a platform for engaging with the language in a more practical and immersive way. By actively participating in such activities, students can broaden their exposure to English and improve their language skills in various contexts. As Participant 7 said that:

“With regards to language exposure naman, is dapat active sila in seeking opportunities outside sa classroom, such as joining English clubs” (FGD_02)

(When it comes to language exposure, they should actively seek opportunities outside the classroom, such as joining English clubs.)

Furthermore, participants recognize implementing interactive activities in English classrooms to enhance language skills. It emphasizes the importance of engaging students in using English effectively to improve their language competence and exposure. As group discussions and debates are highlighted as effective methods to achieve this goal, as they encourage active participation and application of language skills in real-life contexts. As Participant 4 said that:

“Create an engaging activity that requires students to use English effectively since ang target man ani kay to develop the language competence and mas ma expose sila. So, for example no, uhm, group discussions, debates.” (IDI-04)

(Design engaging activities that require students to use English effectively. The goal is to develop their language competence and increase their exposure. For instance, group discussions and debates are effective examples.)

Essential of Employing Engaging Activities to Engage Students. It is essential to employ engaging activities to enhance student engagement in the classroom. These activities can include discussions, group projects, and interactive tasks that stimulate student participation and learning. By engaging in these activities, students can actively participate in the learning process, which can lead to a deeper understanding of the subject matter. Furthermore, these activities can help students develop critical thinking and problem-solving skills, which are essential for their academic and personal growth.

Employ Engaging Activities and Discussion. This is the sixth code of the first issues probed. Employing engaging activities such as speeches, stage plays, radio broadcasting, and role-playing can enhance student engagement. These activities help develop language competence and make learning enjoyable. Incorporating a variety of activities, such as interactive games, encourages students to actively use the language. Integrating active activities throughout classroom discussions ensures continuous language practice. Using interactive activities exposes both students and teachers to the language in a meaningful way.

With regards to that, students believe that teachers should use a variety of interactive and dynamic activities in the classroom to make learning more interesting and effective. Students can benefit from these approaches as they provide practical and engaging ways to learn English. They believe that engaging activities can help students improve their language skills and boost their confidence in using English. Additionally, such activities can make the learning process more enjoyable and memorable for students. As Participant 1 said that:

“Teacher, they must employ engaging activities or scenario no just like kana ganing kuan kanang speech and stage play and another is mag radiobroadcasting I apply nil ana sailang students.” (IDI-01)

(Teachers must employ engaging activities or scenarios, such as speeches, stage plays, and radio broadcasting, to apply to their students.)

Moreover, this statement highlights the importance of using diverse activities to improve students' language skills. By incorporating interactive games and other engaging activities, teachers can help students actively use and practice the language, which can enhance their language competence. These activities can make learning more enjoyable and effective, helping students develop their language competence in a more dynamic and engaging way. As Participant 5 said that:

“Teachers can incorporate a variety of activities no to develop one’s language competence sa students, so these activities it might be interactive games which it can engage students and promote active language use.” (IDI-05)

(Teachers can incorporate a variety of activities to develop students' language competence. These activities may include interactive games that engage students and promote active language use.)

Furthermore, the participant emphasizes the importance of interactive learning for both teachers and students, highlighting that such activities expose both parties to the language. Incorporating interactive activities can enhance language learning by providing a dynamic and immersive experience. They believe that this approach can benefit students by making language learning more engaging and effective. As Participant 10 said that:

“The thing that I can recommend is, to both teacher and student is the interactive learning or activities in which, where the students and teacher are both exposed to the language.” (FGD-05)

(The recommendation I would offer to both teachers and students is interactive learning or activities, where both students and teachers are exposed to the language.)

Engage in Classroom Activities. This is the seventh code of the first issues probed. Engaging in classroom activities such as meaningful discussions expose students to the English language. Instead of prioritizing paper and pen tests, activities like oral recitations and group presentations can be more beneficial. These activities encourage students to use English actively, helping them improve their language competence. By participating in these activities, students can develop their speaking and communication skills in English.

With regards to that, the participants highlight the importance of meaningful discussions as a tool for language exposure and competence development. For students, engaging in such discussions can enhance their understanding and use of the language. It allows them to practice speaking and listening skills in a natural context, aiding in fluency and comprehension. As Participant 2 said that:

“And lastly through ano discussion, having meaningful discussion in which students are directly exposed with the language” (IDI-02)
(And finally, through meaningful discussions, in which students are directly exposed to the language.)

Additionally, learners believed that to enhance language skills, both teachers and students should focus on activities that go beyond traditional methods, such as pen-and-paper tasks. Instead, they should engage in activities that promote reflection and self-improvement. Activities like oral recitation and presentations are recommended as they allow students to practice language skills in a more interactive and meaningful way. As Participant 6 said that:

“My recommendation to both teachers and students in developing one's language competence is they not only prioritize pen and paper activities but also activities where students can contemplate their learning and identify areas that need improvement. So, these activities are oral recitation and presentation.” (FGD-01)

(My recommendation to both teachers and students for developing language competence is to prioritize not only pen-and-paper activities but also activities that encourage students to reflect on their learning and identify areas for improvement. These activities include oral recitation and presentations.)

Communicating with Others and Teachers. This is a key to language development. Engaging with classmates and educators helps students practice and refine their language skills. Through interactions with others, students can receive feedback and guidance, which are vital for improvement. Actively participating in discussions and engaging with teachers and peers allows students to apply their language skills in real-life situations. This engagement fosters confidence and fluency in communication.

Having Communication with Others. Having regular communication with others, both in speaking and writing, is crucial for language development. Engaging in language interactions with peers helps reinforce language skills. Using English in everyday life situations allows for practical application and reinforcement of language skills. Exchanging ideas with others using English helps broaden vocabulary and improve fluency.

Similarly, this response suggests that students can improve their language skills by regularly practicing speaking and writing, as well as engaging in language exchanges with their peers. This practice helps them become more fluent and confident in using the language. Additionally, by interacting with others in English, students can expand their vocabulary and improve their communication skills. Overall, the recommendation emphasizes the importance of regular practice and social interaction in developing language competence. As Participant 5 said that:

“Students can enhance their language competence by regularly practicing speaking and writing, engaging in language exchanges with peers.” (IDI- 05)

(Students can improve their language competence by regularly practicing speaking and writing, as well as by participating in language exchanges with their peers.)

Moreover, the participant suggests that students should actively practice and enhance their language skills by using the language regularly in their daily lives. This includes both speaking and writing. By integrating English into their daily routines, students can develop a natural fluency and comfort with the language, leading to improved communication skills. The student emphasizes the value of immersion and consistent practice in language development. As Participant 8 said that:

“Also, practice or develop their language competence and they should make sure that to use the language in everyday lives.” (FGD-03)

(Also, they should practice and develop their language competence, ensuring consistent use of the language in everyday life.)

Furthermore, learners believe that by exchanging ideas in English, teachers can refine their language abilities and stay updated with current trends and practices in education. Moreover, this practice can foster a supportive community among teachers, where they can share best practices and resources in English. This approach contributes to a more immersive and effective English learning environment for students. As Participant 9 said that:

“I could recommend, if teachers tend to have that kanang exchange of ideas ba towards each other using English language.” (FGD-04)

“I could recommend that teachers engage in exchanging ideas with each other using the English language.”

Student and Teacher Engagement. Student and teacher engagement is essential for effective language learning. This can be fostered through various means, including students asking questions and teachers initiating discussions in English.

Interactive activities should be incorporated into the learning process to encourage active participation and engagement between students and teachers. These activities not only enhance language skills but also create a more dynamic and immersive learning environment.

In connection, the participants believe that in discussions, both students and teachers should engage in a reciprocal exchange of questions and answers. Students are encouraged to ask questions to deepen their understanding, while teachers play an active role in

answering and also posing questions to stimulate critical thinking. This approach fosters a dynamic learning environment where both parties are actively involved in the learning process. As Participant 3 said that:

“Sa both kanang kuan learner and teacher is kanang specially sa discussion na, kay kana ganing vice versa perminte ang strategy like the student will ask and the teacher will answer tapos si teacher napud mag ask and the student will answer.” (IDI-03)

(For both learners and teachers, especially in discussions, the strategy should be reciprocal, where students ask questions and the teacher answers, and then the teacher asks questions and the students answer.)

Moreover, the learners recognized that students should actively participate in interactions with teachers or among peers using English, which can enhance their language skills and expose them more to the language. By engaging in conversations and discussions in English, students can improve their fluency and vocabulary while also gaining exposure to different ways the language is used. Additionally, these interactions can help them become more confident in using English in various contexts, which is crucial for their language development. As participant 7 said that:

“Another is kanang mag kuan gani sila uhm student and teacher interaction gani or teacher-student engagement gani using the English language para mas ma develop nila ilang language competence and mas ma expose sila sa language.” (FGD-02)

(Another aspect is for them to engage in student- teacher interactions or teacher-student engagements using the English language to further develop their language competence and to be more exposed to the language.)

Furthermore, the students recognize the significance of engaging in activities that promote the use of English, particularly through student-teacher interactions. By participating in such activities, students can actively practice and improve their language skills. Additionally, these interactions create opportunities for students to engage with the language in a meaningful way, which can enhance their language competence. The use of English in these interactions also helps students become more comfortable and confident in using the language. As Participant 1 said that:

“Importante pud no nga si teacher is mag employ syag mga activity nga gagamit ang mga students ug English language or kanang student-teacher interaction” (IDI-01)

(It is also important for the teacher to employ activities that involve students using the English language, such as student-teacher interaction.)

Emphasizing the Importance of Language Learning through Real-World Activities. Incorporating real-world activities into language learning is essential for students' development. These activities should be relevant to everyday situations, allowing students to apply what they learn in class to real-life contexts. By developing engaging activities, teachers can make language learning more enjoyable and effective for students. These activities should be given significant importance in language learning curricula to ensure students acquire practical language skills.

Having the Application to Real-World Setting. This is the first code of the second issues probed. Having the application to real-world settings is crucial for language learning. Providing opportunities for students to experience real-life communication scenarios and contexts can significantly enhance their language skills. By incorporating real-world scenarios and activities, students are more likely to retain what they have learned. This ensures that students not only learn the language but also understand its practical applications in real-life situations.

With regards to that, the participants report the abundance of learning materials but points out a deficiency in real-world application for students to apply their knowledge. This lack of practical application could hinder their ability to fully grasp and internalize the language skills they are learning. As a student, this feedback underscores the importance of incorporating real-world scenarios and activities into the learning process. As Participant 1 said that:

“As what I've observed that there are lots of learning materials but having a lack of real world application for students para matagaan silage chance to utilize what they have learned” (IDI-01)

(As I have observed, there are many learning materials available, but there is a lack of real-world application for students to have the chance to utilize what they have learned.)

Moreover, participants believe that students should participate in reporting and demonstration teaching as part of their language learning. It implies that these activities are already common in educational settings. By engaging in these activities, students, particularly future educators, can enhance their language skills and practice effective communication. The emphasis is on practical application and real-world scenarios, which are essential for language competence development. As Participant 2 said that:

“They could do reportings in which I believe na gina practice na so sa education students they could add the demo teaching because through this we future educators we are able to really use the language in which we are practicing our self to really communicate” (IDI-02)

(They could engage in reporting, which I believe is already being practiced in education. Students could also include demonstration

teaching, as through this, future educators can effectively use the language, practicing to communicate proficiently.)

Furthermore, learners recognize creating real-life communication opportunities would be beneficial for students. It implies that students should have chances to use English in practical, everyday situations beyond the classroom. By engaging in such activities, students can improve their language skills and become more confident in

using English in real-world contexts. It also implies that the use of English should not be limited to the classroom but should extend to various real-life scenarios to enhance language learning. As Participant 4 said that:

“And then siguro mag provide silage opportunities no for real-life communication.” (IDI-04)

(And perhaps they could provide opportunities for real-life communication.)

Also, students emphasize the importance of incorporating engaging activities, such as oral recitations and real-world examples, to enhance students' long-term retention of English language skills. By including these activities, teachers can create more dynamic and interactive learning environments. Students believe that this can also help students see the practical applications of their language learning, making the lessons more meaningful and memorable. As Participant 9 said that:

“They should involve more activities like oral recitation or kanang real-word kanang examples or activity na kanang, help students retain or to have that longer retention when it comes to learning the English language po.” (FGD-04)

(They should incorporate more activities such as oral recitation or real-world examples that help students retain English language skills for longer periods.)

Developing Engaging Activities. This is the second code of the second issues probed. Developing engaging activities is crucial in helping students understand the importance of English for their future. By creating authentic tasks and projects that require English communication skills, teachers can motivate students to actively participate. It's also important to integrate technology resources into the curriculum to make learning more interactive and relevant.

Similarly, participant believe that engaging students with authentic tasks and projects that require English communication skills can motivate them to use the language beyond the classroom. It implies that practical, real-world applications of English can enhance students' interest and proficiency. By providing such activities, teachers can create a more immersive and meaningful learning experience, encouraging students to apply their language skills in various contexts. As Participant 7 said that:

“And additionally, creating authentic tasks and projects that require English communication skills can also motivate students to engage with the language beyond traditional classroom settings.” (FGD-02)

(And also, developing authentic tasks and projects that require English communication skills can motivate students to interact with the language outside of traditional classroom environments.)

Moreover, the participants acknowledge the importance of integrating authentic materials and technology resources into language learning activities, emphasizing their inclusion in the curriculum. It implies that using real-world materials and technology can enhance the relevance and effectiveness of language learning. By incorporating authentic materials and technology, teachers can create more engaging and meaningful learning experiences for students. As Participant 8 said that:

“There should be integration of authentic materials and technology resources when making an activity, this should be included in the curriculum.” (FGD-03)

(Authentic materials and technological resources should be integrated into activities and included in the curriculum.)

Given Importance in Language Learning. This is the third code of the second issues probed. Teachers can design activities that encourage students to reflect on how language learning can benefit them personally. This can helps students see the relevance of language skills in their daily lives and motivates them to engage more actively in language learning. By emphasizing the importance of language learning, students are more likely to see it as a valuable skill worth investing time and effort into. This can lead to improved language proficiency and a deeper understanding of the language.

With regards to that, the learners emphasize the crucial role of prioritizing language learning to advance one's proficiency. By recognizing the significance of language acquisition, students can actively engage in activities that enhance their language skills and broaden their exposure to the language. This promotes a deeper understanding and appreciation for the language, leading to improved competence and fluency over time. As Participant 3 said that:

“Mas I enhance or i-top level pa gani jud in terms of language learning gani like tagaan jud importansya ang pag learn sa language para ma enhance pud nato or ma develop ang language competence ug syempre ma expose ta sa language.” (IDI-03)

(To further enhance or reach a higher level in language learning, it is essential to prioritize the importance of learning the language. This will not only enhance and develop our language competence but also expose us to the language.)

Similarly, the participant recognizes the importance of engaging students in activities that highlight the relevance of English language skills for their future. Students should be encouraged to see the practical applications of language learning in their lives beyond the classroom. Incorporating activities that mirror real-world scenarios can enhance students' motivation and understanding. By emphasizing the practical benefits of language skills, students are more likely to stay motivated and engaged in their learning. As Participant 4 said that:

“So, kuan i-encourage pud or kanang mag employ silag activities nga kanang maka feel silag, maka feel sila nga dapat nil ani tunan kay gamit kayu ni sailahang future endeavors.” (IDI-04)

(They should also encourage or employ activities that make students feel that they should take this seriously because it will be very useful for their future endeavors.)

Essentials of Seminars and Immersion Programs to Develop Students' Language Proficiency. These initiatives collectively create a more holistic approach to language learning, encouraging students to actively engage and apply their language skills in real-world scenarios. Through seminars, immersion programs, and a structured policy, students can enhance their language proficiency and gain confidence in using English effectively.

Conducting of Seminars. This is the first code of the third issues probed. This is crucial for enhancing students' language competence and exposing them to the language in different contexts. These seminars can be formulated to directly immerse students in language-rich environments. Webinars focusing on the importance of language competence and exposure can also be beneficial. Such events provide students with additional knowledge and promote meaningful learning experiences.

With regards to that, the participant suggests that CHED should conduct seminars to enhance students' language competence and exposure to English. Seminars can serve as valuable opportunities for students to immerse themselves in the language and develop their skills. By participating in these seminars, students can gain a deeper understanding of the language and its practical applications in various contexts. As Participant 1 said that:

“And since we are talking about CHED, mag kuan silag seminars like kanang seminars nga mas ma enhance sa mga students ang ilang language compentece ug kanang mas ma expose pa sila sa English language.” (IDI-01)

(And since we are talking about CHED, they must conduct seminars that will enhance students' language competence and expose them more to the English language.)

Moreover, the participant emphasizes the importance of direct exposure to the English language, indicating a recognition of the role that immersion and practical application play in language learning. The student underscores the value of immersive learning experiences outside the classroom, which can significantly enhance language competence. It implies that such initiatives could provide valuable opportunities for students to practice and apply their English language skills in real-world contexts. As Participant 2 said that:

“I would really personally recommend na CHED would formulate a seminars or trainings for students in which in this seminars or trainings the students will directly exposed with the English language.” (IDI-02)

(I personally recommend that CHED organize seminars or training sessions for students, where they will be directly exposed to the English language.)

Also, the participant believe that students should have more exposure to English, possibly through webinars or focused activities, to improve their language skills. It implies that current exposure may not be sufficient for enhancing competence. To contextualize this for students, you could explain the benefits of such exposure, like gaining a better grasp of the language and being better prepared for future language use in various contexts. As Participant 3 said that:

“And i-expose pa silag maayu sa language just like kanang mga webinar or kanang activities gani nga mag focus sa mga importante nga aspect sa English language like kanang sa pag enhance sa ilang competence and exposure sa language.” (IDI-03)

(They should be further exposed to the language, such as through webinars or activities that focus on important aspects of the English language, like enhancing their competence and exposure to the language.)

Furthermore, the participant response suggests that CHED should provide more specific activities like seminars or other language exposure activities to enhance students' knowledge and facilitate meaningful learning experiences. By suggesting specific actions, the response shows a proactive approach to improving language learning. It also emphasizes the importance of meaningful learning experiences, indicating a focus on practical application and engagement. As Participant 10 said that:

“The recommendations that I need to give to CHED is, provide more specific activities like seminars or other activities which involve language exposure and so that students gain the knowledge and in that way students will experience meaningful learning.” (FGD- 05)

(My recommendations to CHED are to offer more specific activities, such as seminars or other language exposure activities, to enhance students' knowledge and facilitate meaningful learning experiences.)

Having Immersion Programs. This is the second code of the third issues probed. Having immersion programs is crucial as it exposes

students to an English-speaking working environment, providing practical experience. These programs should be promoted alongside internships and study abroad opportunities to enhance language skills. Immersion programs offer a unique chance to use English in real-life situations, fostering language competence. By participating in such programs, students can develop a deeper understanding and appreciation for the language.

With regards to that, the participant believe that the Commission on Higher Education should actively encourage programs that immerse students in English- speaking environments. This would likely involve initiatives such as study abroad programs or internships in English-speaking countries. Such programs could be valuable for students seeking to improve their English proficiency and broaden their perspectives. As participant 4 said that:

“The Commission on Higher Education should promote immersion programs like kanang mag spend ug time ang mga student in English-speaking environments.”(IDI-04)

(The Commission on Higher Education should promote immersion programs where students spend time in English-speaking environments.)

In addition, the participant suggests that CHED could promote various programs, such as English language immersion, internships, and study abroad opportunities, to expose students to authentic English environments. These programs are aimed at providing students with firsthand experience in using English in real-life situations, which can significantly enhance their language skills and cultural understanding. By promoting such programs, CHED can help students develop a deeper appreciation for the English language and its practical applications. As Participant 7 said that:

“CHED could promote English language immersion programs, internships, and study abroad opportunities to expose students to authentic English environments” (FGD-02)

(The Commission on Higher Education (CHED) could advocate for the implementation of English language immersion programs, internships, and study abroad opportunities to provide students with exposure to authentic English-speaking environments.)

Developing Policy on English Language Proficiency. This is the third code of the third issues probed. Developing a policy on English language proficiency involves implementing measures that prioritize language competence. By this, students are encouraged to prioritize their language development and strive for proficiency. This policy ensures that students are adequately prepared for academic and professional environments where English proficiency is essential. It also serves as a benchmark for measuring students' language skills and tracking their progress over time.

With regards to that, the participant suggests that implementing policies focused on English language competence is important, possibly through measures like English proficiency tests. For students, this could mean having clear standards and expectations for English proficiency. Incorporating such tests into the curriculum could motivate students to improve their language skills. Additionally, it could provide a structured way to measure language growth and offer targeted support where needed. As Participant 4 said that:

“They can implement policy that prioritize English language competence or ma develop ilang language competence, this could include incorporating English proficiency tests.” (IDI-04)

(They can implement policies that prioritize English language competence or develop their language proficiency. This could include incorporating English proficiency tests.)

Also, the participant suggests that including English language proficiency exams in the curriculum can motivate students to focus on improving their language skills. Students may see these exams as important benchmarks for their language development. It could also provide a clear path for students to track their progress in language proficiency. By integrating such exams into the curriculum, it can create a structured approach to language learning, with defined goals and outcomes. As Participant 7 said that:

“Additionally, incorporating English language proficiency exams as part of the curriculum can motivate students to prioritize language development.” (FGD-2)

(Additionally, incorporating English language proficiency exams into the curriculum can motivate students to prioritize their language development.)

Data Integration of the Salient Quantitative and Qualitative Findings. The current study, which examines the relationship between language exposure and language competence among English major students at a local college, utilizes a mixed methods approach through a convergent parallel design. The fifth research question addresses the corroboration of findings from both the quantitative and qualitative phases. Table 5 presents the key findings from both phases, with the first column outlining the focal aspects of the study. The second and third columns display the quantitative and qualitative findings, respectively. Quantitative results typically reflect indicators with the highest means, while the qualitative findings consist of identified responses that either confirm or disconfirm the quantitative data. The fourth column indicates the nature of the data integration, while the fifth column presents the axiological implications derived from the data presented in the preceding columns.

Language Exposure. In the quantitative phase, under the indicator of home, the specific item was rated by the participants as moderate

engaging activities that English language is usually used. This result is connected with the qualitative findings, which is categorized as having the application to real-world setting, specifically in the core idea providing opportunities for real-life communication scenario and context, under the essential theme of emphasizing the importance of language learning through real-world activities. It is safe then to say that the qualitative merges the quantitative.

Table 5. Joint Display of Salient Quantitative and Qualitative Findings

ASPECT OR FOCAL POINT	QUANTITATIVE FINDINGS	QUALITATIVE FINDINGS	NATURE OF DATA INTEGRATION	AXIOLOGICAL IMPLICATIONS
Language Exposure of English Major Students	On the table 2 the indicator <i>home</i> with an overall mean of 2.85 specifically in the item number 3- <i>engage activities that English language is usually used</i> (2.81; moderate)	On the table 2.1 category of <i>having the application to real-world setting</i> specifically in the core idea 3- <i>providing opportunities for real-life communication scenario and context.</i>	Merging-converging	The moderate rating for home indicates that English major students usually engage real-world setting using English language to communicate.
	On the table 2 the indicator <i>friends</i> with an overall average mean of 3.32 specifically in the item number 2- <i>communicate with others in the language of English</i> (3.31; moderate)	On the table 2.1 category of <i>using English in daily lives</i> specifically in the core idea 1- <i>using English in talking and communicating with others to enhance one's language competence</i>	Merging-converging	The moderate rating for friends indicates that English major students communicate with others using English language to enhance their language competence.
	On the table 2 the indicator <i>school</i> with an overall average mean of 4.17 specifically in the item number 4- <i>speak verbally in English language when doing homework, projects, or presentation</i> (4.16; high)	On the table 2.1 category of <i>class reporting using English language</i> specifically in the core idea 1- <i>speaking English in delivering class reporting.</i>	Merging-converging	The high rating for school indicates that English major students purposely used the English language in the academic context such in expressing their ideas fluently or making tasks.
	On the table 2 the indicator <i>media</i> with an overall average mean of 4.03 specifically in the item number 5- <i>watch TV shows and movies in English language</i> (4.31; high)	On the table 2.1 category of <i>watching English movies</i> specifically in the core idea 2- <i>opting to watch movies with English subtitles.</i>	Merging-converging	The high rating for media indicates that English major students underscore the impact of digital resources and advancements in enhancing their language competence.
Language Competence of English Major Students	On the table 2 the indicator <i>reading</i> with an overall average mean of 3.69 specifically in the item number 2- <i>understand most of the vocabulary in English texts</i> (3.64; high)	On the table 2.1 category of <i>making reading a habit</i> specifically in the core idea 2- <i>reading books to discover new terms and words which will enhance students' vocabulary.</i>	Merging-converging	The high rating for reading indicates that English major students emphasizes the reading as a practice in discovering and enhancing competency in English language.

	On the table 2 the indicator <i>writing</i> with an overall average mean of 3.71 specifically in the item number 3- <i>write creatively and expressively in English</i> (3.73; high)	On the table 2.1 category of <i>participation with school activities</i> specifically in the core idea 1- <i>practicing writing essays and short stories to express themselves through writing.</i>	Merging-converging	The high rating for writing indicates that English major students emphasizes the writing ability to express their ideas effectively in a creative manner.
	On the table 2 the indicator <i>speaking</i> with an overall average mean of 3.58 specifically in the item number 5- <i>participate effectively in English discussions and conversation</i> (3.66; high).	On the table 2.1 category of <i>engage in classroom activities</i> specifically in the core idea 1- <i>having meaningful discussion making the students be exposed with the English language.</i>	Merging-converging	The high rating for writing indicates that English major students emphasizes the role of speaking to express themselves in the role of conversing and effective communication .
	On the table 2 the indicator <i>listening</i> with an overall mean of 3.64 specifically in the item number 5- <i>listen and comprehending different genres of English speech (news, interviews, presentations, etc.)</i> (3.72; high).	On the table 2.1 category of <i>employ engaging activities and discussion</i> specifically in the core idea 1- <i>employing engaging activities like speech and stage play, radio broadcasting, and role play to engage more the students.</i>	Merging-converging	The high rating for listening indicates that English major students emphasizes the listening as pivotal factor in comprehending various source of information in dealing with various contexts.
	On the table 2 the indicator <i>comprehension</i> with an overall average of 3.86 specifically in the item number 2- <i>infer and interpret meaning from English texts</i> (3.81; high)	On the table 2.1 category of <i>reading and engaging various literary texts</i> specifically in the core idea 3- <i>analyzing literary texts.</i>	Merging-converging	The high rating for comprehension indicates that English major students underscore the role of comprehension to understand various materials related to the language context.

In the quantitative phase, under the indicator of friends, the specific item was rated by the participants as moderate communicating with others in the language of English. This result is connected with the qualitative findings, which is categorized as using English in daily lives, specifically in the core idea using English in talking and communicating with others to enhance one’s language competence, under the essential theme of constant practice with the language and be open with feedback.

Hence, this can be viewed that the qualitative merges with the quantitative.

Furthermore, in the quantitative phase, under the indicator of school, the specific item was rated by the participants as high speaking verbally in English language when doing homework, projects, or presentation. This result is connected with the qualitative findings, which is categorized as class reporting using English language, specifically in the core idea speaking English in delivering class reporting, under the essential theme of exposure with classroom tasks and activities. Thus, this can be viewed that the quantitative and

qualitative merges.

Moreover, in the quantitative phase, under the indicator of media, the specific item was rated by the participants as high watching TV shows and movies in English language. This result is connected with the qualitative findings, which is categorized as watching English movies, specifically in the core idea opting to watch movies with English subtitles, under the essential theme of exposure with media having English as the medium. This can be viewed that both quantitative and qualitative merges.

Language competence. In the quantitative phase, under the indicator of reading, the specific item was rated by the participants as high understanding most of the vocabulary in English texts. This result is connected with the qualitative findings, which is categorized as making reading a habit, specifically in the core idea reading books to discover new terms and words which will enhance students' vocabulary, under the essential theme of constant practice with the language and be open with feedback. It is safe then to say that the qualitative merges the quantitative.

In addition, in the quantitative phase, under the indicator of writing, the specific item was rated by the participants as high writing creatively and expressively in English. This result is connected with the qualitative findings, which is categorized as participation with school activities, specifically in the core idea practicing writing essays and short stories to express themselves through writing, under the essential them of one must have exposure with varied language activities and resources. Hence, this can be viewed that the qualitative merges with the quantitative.

Similarly, in the quantitative phase, under the indicator of speaking, the specific item was rated by the participants as high participating effectively in English discussions and conversation. This result is connected with the qualitative findings, which is categorized as engage in classroom activities, specifically in the core idea of having meaningful discussion making the students be exposed with the English language, under the essential theme of essential of employing engaging activities to engage students. This can be viewed that the quantitative and qualitative merges.

Moreover, in the quantitative phase, under the indicator of listening, the specific item was rated by the participants as high listening and comprehending different genres of English speech (news, interviews, presentations, etc.). This result is connected with the qualitative findings, which is categorized as employ engaging activities and discussion, specifically in the core idea employing engaging activities like speech and stage play, radio broadcasting, and role play to engage more the students, under the essential theme of essential of employing engaging activities to engage students. Thus, this can be viewed that the quantitative and qualitative merges.

Furthermore, in the quantitative phase, under the indicator of comprehension, the specific item was rated by the participants as high inferring and interpret meaning from English texts. This result is connected with the qualitative findings, which is categorized as reading and engaging various literary texts, specifically in the core idea analyzing literary texts, under the essential theme of exposure with media having English as the medium. This can be stated that the quantitative and qualitative merges.

Conclusions

Based on the findings of the study, the following conclusions were drawn:

First, the level of language exposure among English major student is high in terms of school and media, while the indicator home and friends are moderate, but still the overall result is high. Also, the level of language competence among English major students is also high in term of reading, writing, speaking, listening, and comprehension. Hence, this indicate that the indicators of language exposure and language competence are always manifested by the English major students.

Second, the findings revealed the significant relationship of language exposure and language competence among English major students using the Mean, R-Value and P-Value. It was revealed that both variables are rejected hence, there is significant relationship between language exposure and language competence among English major students.

Third, the thematic analysis of the qualitative data was conducted based on responses obtained from in-depth interviews (IDI) and focus group discussions (FGD). This analysis provided additional insights into the lived experiences and coping mechanisms of English major students, specifically regarding how exposure to the English language can enhance their language competence. Qualitatively, English major students have been experiencing different situations that contribute to their language exposure, aiming to enhance their language competence. The following themes were emerged: level of competence with English language used, exposure with classroom tasks and activities, exposure with media having English as the medium, exposure of English language in different contexts, deteriorating knowledge with lexicon, degrading interpersonal skills with English, and emerging development with the language.

Fourth, from the participants responses, other themes are identified which show the insights shared of English major students with regards to the effectiveness being exposed with English language on their language competence. The following are the themes: constant practice with the language and be open with feedback, one must have exposure with varied language activities and resources, essential of employing engaging activities to engage students, communicating with friends and teachers, emphasizing the importance of language learning through real-world activities, and essentials of seminars and immersion programs to develop students' language proficiency.

Lastly, to comprehensively assess the impact of language exposure on the language competence of English major students, the

responses were analyzed thematically to validate the qualitative findings of the study. The results from both phases were integrated according to the planned approach. The quantitative results provided insights into the levels of language exposure (LE) and language competence (LC) among participants, which were then cross-referenced with the qualitative data. Both sets of findings converged, confirming that language exposure significantly influences students' language competence across various dimensions. This convergence underscores the enhancement of students' abilities to understand nuances, engage in discourse, and apply linguistic functions effectively within different contexts.

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations were being drawn:

Since the level of perceived language exposure among English major students reveals that, among the four indicators, the home is the lowest mean among them, which indicates that English major students are unlikely using English at home which can affect to the development of their competence with English language. Less exposure to English language at home may result to have limited opportunities to practice and develop your English language skills. This could potentially lead to difficulties in understanding and communicating in English, especially in academic or professional settings where English proficiency is important. To address this issue, first, learners must engage themselves in an immersive environment by surrounding themselves with English-language media such as books, movies, and music. Additionally, they must seek out online resources and courses to practice reading, writing, speaking, and listening skills. Engaging in conversations with friends, family, or language exchange partners in English would also be beneficial. Lastly, setting aside dedicated time each day for language practice and setting specific, achievable goals would help track progress and maintain motivation.

Additionally, since the level of perceived language competence among English major students reveals that among the five indicator of language competence, speaking is the lowest mean among of them, which indicate that it can negatively affect your ability to effectively communicate and comprehend spoken English. This can lead to challenges in academic, professional, and social contexts where English proficiency is required. To address this issue and improve competence in speaking English, it is recommended to engage in regular conversations with native speakers or participate in language exchange programs. Additionally, practicing pronunciation and intonation by listening to English media, such as podcasts or audiobooks, can be beneficial. Joining conversation clubs or attending speaking-focused workshops can provide structured opportunities for practice. Lastly, seeking feedback from language teacher or instructors and actively incorporating their suggestions into practice can also help improve speaking skills.

Moreover, in the qualitative phase results on the lived experiences and coping mechanism of English major students with regards to their language exposure in pursuit of enhancing their language competence particular in English language, students must expose themselves in different environment or context where English was spoken and used. Exposing oneself with classroom task and activity helps enhance learning by providing practical application of concepts and fostering active engagement in the learning process. Exposure to media with English as the medium can improve language proficiency by providing real-life examples of language use and enhancing vocabulary and comprehension skills. Additionally, exposure to English language in different contexts helps learners adapt their language skills to various situations, improving their overall communication abilities. It also broadens their understanding of cultural nuances and diverse uses of English, enhancing their language proficiency.

Consequently, those shared insight from English major students with regards to the effectiveness of language exposure may help them to address their needs in enhancing their language competence. Constant practice with the language and being open to feedback can improve language exposure and competence by providing opportunities to refine language skills and receive guidance for improvement. This approach helps learners identify and address areas of weakness, leading to more effective language use and communication. Additionally, exposure to varied language activities and resources enhances language exposure and competence by providing diverse contexts for learning and practice. It helps learners develop a more comprehensive understanding of the language and improves their ability to communicate effectively in different situations. Lastly, employing engaging activities and communicating with friends and teachers can enhance language exposure and competence by providing interactive and meaningful language practice. These activities promote active engagement with the language, leading to improved language skills and fluency.

In addition, the researcher wanted to recommend, regular and meaningful interaction with native English speakers, as this can enhance language exposure and competence by providing authentic language use examples. This exposure helps learners understand how the language is used in real-life contexts, improving their language skills. In addition, interacting with native speakers allows learners to practice speaking and listening skills, leading to increased fluency and confidence. These interactions can greatly benefit language learners in their journey to proficiency.

Lastly, integration of interactive tools and websites using emerging technologies. This is one of the effective ways to enhance language exposure and language competence as we are in the 21st century where technology is dominant in terms of learning. By this, it provides learners with engaging and interactive learning experiences, making language learning more enjoyable and effective. Additionally, these technologies provide access to a diverse array of authentic language materials, including videos and interactive exercises, which can enhance language competence. Moreover, interactive tools frequently offer immediate feedback, enabling learners to monitor their progress and refine their language skills. Incorporating these technologies into language learning can result in more immersive, efficient, and personalized learning experiences.

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